

Superior thermoelectric performance of SiGe nanowires epitaxially integrated into thermal micro-harvesters

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Abstract:

Semiconductor nanowires have demonstrated fascinating properties with applications in a wide range of fields, including energy and information technologies. Particularly, increasing attention has focused on SiGe nanowires for applications in thermoelectric generation. In this work, a bottom-up Vapour-Liquid-Solid Chemical Vapour Deposition methodology is employed to integrate heavily boron-doped SiGe nanowires on thermoelectric generators. Thermoelectrical properties - i.e. electrical and thermal conductivities and Seebeck coefficient - of grown nanowires were fully characterized at temperatures ranging from 300 to 600 K, allowing the complete determination of the Figure-of-merit, zT , with obtained values of 0.4 at 600 K for optimally doped nanowires. A correlation between doping level, thermoelectric performance, and elemental distribution was established employing advanced elemental mapping (synchrotron-based nano-X-ray fluorescence). Moreover, the operation of p-doped SiGe NWs integrated in silicon micromachined thermoelectrical generators is shown over standalone and series- and parallel-connected arrays. Maximum open circuit voltage of 13.8 mV and power output as high as 15.6 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ are reached in series and parallel configurations, respectively, operating upon thermal gradients generated with hot sources at 200°C and air flows of 1.5 m/s. These results pave the way for direct application of SiGe nanowire-based micro-thermoelectric generators in the field of the Internet of Things.

Highlights:

- Integration of bottom-up grown SiGe nanowires for silicon-based heat microscavengers.
- Correlation between doping level, dopant distribution and thermoelectric properties in SiGe nanowires.
- Complete thermoelectrical characterization of integrated SiGe nanowires.
- Evaluation of the power output of combinations of series and parallel harvesting devices.

Keywords: Silicon-Germanium, Thermoelectric, Integration, Nanowire, Micro/nano-generator, X-ray fluorescence, Tip-enhanced Raman spectroscopy

1. Introduction:

The Internet of Things (IoT) is intended to be a core technology for the next digital revolution. Wireless interconnection of trillions of delocalized sensors will require the development of robust micropower sources [1]. While primary batteries are nowadays the preferred solution, the current scenario cannot be extended much longer, as the exponentially growing number of connected devices require too complex logistics, both for their periodic replacement and disposal of such batteries. In this context, energy harvesting combined with small energy buffers (rechargeable batteries or capacitors) represents a more sustainable alternative to single-use batteries [2–4]. In particular, thermoelectric harvesters are solid-state devices capable of directly converting waste heat into electricity, with efficiencies in the range of 1–10%. Among their main advantages, an absence of movable parts, high reliability, and the recently explored possibility of miniaturization make them promising candidates to power the IoT revolution [5–7].

The efficiency of a ThermoElectric (TE) system is measured using the so-called zT *Figure of Merit*, a dimensionless parameter that relates the main TE properties of the materials as $zT = S^2\sigma T/\kappa$, where S is the Seebeck coefficient, σ electrical conductivity, and κ its thermal conductivity. Although the thermoelectric effect is known since the 19th century, currently best-performing TE materials are still based on scarce, expensive, environmentally harmful, and toxic elements like bismuth, tellurium, and lead-based materials. Nevertheless, in recent years, the paradigm of thermoelectricity has radically changed thanks to the introduction of low-dimensional materials. Nano-structuring enables tuning some bulk properties of the materials - such as the thermal conductivity through phonon scattering - while keeping the electronic performance. Consequently, materials previously discarded - primarily due to a large bulk thermal conductivity - have regained significant interest [8–11]. In particular, increasing attention has been focused on Si and SiGe nanostructures for thermoelectric generation after its recent successful implementation in miniaturized devices [12–23]. While it has already been reported the potential of Si for integration in state-of-the-art microfabricated ThermoElectric Generators (μ TEGs), the implementation of SiGe NWs - more desirable thanks to a further reduced thermal conductivity and, consequently, better TE Figure-of-Merit - still represents a challenge [24].

Thermoelectric property tuning of semiconductor nanowires is typically undergone through adjustments of the doping level. Nevertheless, fine-tuning the dopant content in VLS-CVD NWs growth is a challenge itself since a deep understanding of the interplay among the different gas precursors and the impact on the vapour-liquid-solid phase is required. In this work, p-type doping of SiGe NWs was performed by controlling the flow of a boron-rich gas precursor (B_2H_6). However, the addition of an excess of boron impurities is known to have side effects in the growth of Si and Ge NWs that must be considered, such as nanoparticle precipitation [25,26] or tapering either by catalyst precipitation or lateral growth [27,28]. Previous approaches to grow p-doped SiGe have so far been limited to low temperatures (400°C), resulting in slow growth rates and/or lack of epitaxy [29], which limits the suitability for integration of such NWs in silicon devices due to the resulting short lengths ($< 1 \mu m$) or misalignments. In particular, tapering effects caused by excess of B_2H_6 were shown to be manageable adding variable amounts of hydrochloric acid (HCl) during the NW growth process [30]. Nonetheless, increasing the partial pressure of HCl during the CVD process is detrimental for the NW growth rate, as the catalyst surface bonds covered by Cl atoms

have higher activation energies than the H ones, thus partially hindering the dissociation and absorption of the precursor gases.

To put some light on all these issues, the effect of the concentration of some gas precursors – namely hydrochloric acid (HCl) and diborane (B_2H_6) – in the SiGe NW growth is studied in order to determine the optimal parameters. Precise insight into the chemical composition along the p-doped SiGe NWs (with a precision below 100 nm) is achieved employing a synchrotron source for nano X-ray fluorescence (XRF) mapping (carried out at the ESRF facilities) and Tip-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (TERS). The functionality of the optimal NWs is proved by their integration into silicon micromachined devices. To the best of our knowledge, this work represents the first thermoelectric characterization of a fully integrated individual SiGe NW. Finally, the performance of a device including arrays of these optimal NWs working as a waste heat harvester is evaluated when connected in series and parallel in a complete power generation system.

2. Results and discussion:

2.1. Optimization of the epitaxial integration of heavily doped SiGe NWs

SiGe NWs were grown perpendicular to $\langle 111 \rangle$ silicon substrates through means of a bottom-up approach (CVD-VLS). The procedure starts with the deposition of Au NP of 80 ± 15 nm in diameter, which act as catalysts for the decomposition of the gas precursors introduced in the CVD chamber. The preferential epitaxial growth in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction of the NWs yields perpendicular alignment with respect to the device surfaces. This monolithic integration results in virtually null electrical and thermal contact resistances, as already proven with Si NWs in previous works [31].

Table 1. VLS-CVD parameters used in the growth of SiGe NWs.

Parameter	Temperature	650 °C
	Total pressure	330 Pa
	Growth time	120 min
	Total gas flow	1250 sscm*
Partial pressures	H ₂	318 Pa
	SiH ₄	5.35 Pa
	GeH ₄	0.214 Pa
	HCl	7.5 – 9.3 Pa
	B ₂ H ₆	4 - 20 mPa
Gas ratios	GeH ₄ /(GeH ₄ + SiH ₄)	0.0385
	SiH ₄ :HCl	1.5 – 1.75
	SiH ₄ :B ₂ H ₆	1100 - 200

*Standard cubic centimetres per minute (Ncm³/min)

Table 1 shows the different gas concentrations in the reactor explored with the aim of identifying the impact of the different species on the shape and performance of the NWs. Regarding HCl, Figure 1a-c shows SiGe NWs grown over Si (111) seeded substrates at different HCl to SiH₄ ratios (0, 0.75, and 1.5, respectively) while fixing the rest of conditions (to those of Table 1). Three fairly different scenarios are observed. In the case in which no HCl is incorporated, NWs are scarce and misaligned, showing short

lengths (in the order of one micron) and sharp cone shapes (diameters going from 100 nm in the tip up to 800 nm in the base). When increasing HCl:SiH₄ ratio to 0.75 ([HCl] = 3.94 Pa), the NWs grow well-packed and generally aligned but present thick diameters and a still pronounced tapering of about 100 nm/μm. Bulky bottom layers, most likely attributable to polycrystalline SiGe, are clearly observed in both HCl:SiH₄=0 and 0.75 scenarios. Finally, in the case of HCl:SiH₄ = 1.5 ([HCl] = 7.78 Pa), NWs present higher density and smaller diameters (~ 60 nm). Moreover, NWs are no longer tapered and are mainly aligned in the favorable directions of growth. Finally, the polycrystalline SiGe layer formation is notably suppressed (see Figure 1c).

Figure 1. Cross section SEM images of SiGe NWs grown on equally seeded substrate with different HCl concentrations (**a-c**) and different diborane concentrations (**d-f**), while rest of conditions were fixed.

Fixing the HCl to SiH₄ ratio at 1.5, i.e. enabling aligned NWs, a study of the effects of B₂H₆ partial pressures in the growth chamber was performed in order to maximize the doping level. Figure 1d-f show the cross-section of three different growths in which the diborane partial pressure was gradually increased from 4.9 mPa to 19 mPa. Under these conditions, the growth rate was overall estimated to be 100 nm/min. For very low partial pressures (4.9 mPa), NWs grow without significant tapering effects although kinks and inhomogeneous landscape is observed. At intermediate partial pressures (10-13 mPa) the alignment of NWs is clearly improved and fewer defects can be observed. In addition, an increased roughness of the NWs is present, likely promoted by Au NP sliding along the surface. Finally, for higher concentrations of diborane (19 mPa), SiGe NWs present smoother surfaces, thicker diameters, and visible tapering. Likely due to the strong tapering, no Au NP seed was found at the tip of these NWs.

Figure 2. Average atomic fraction of Ge (upper scale) and Au (lower scale) measured from the XRF mapping of each analyzed sample (excluding NWs gold-rich tips) as a function of the diborane (B_2H_6) partial pressure used and two different HCl to Si ratios (also indicated at the scatter labeling). The rest of the conditions were set constant.

Chemical analysis using nano-XRF revealed the differences between NWs of growths under different diborane partial pressures. Elemental concentrations for the different growth conditions were calculated from the integrated XRF signals of individual NWs (excluding the Au tips) and averaged with at least two NWs from the same growth. Figure 2 shows the atomic fraction of Ge and Au as a function of the diborane partial pressure and two different HCl:SiH₄ ratios of 1.5 and 1.75 (the complete list of experimental conditions can be found in *Table Suppl. 2*). Ge concentration is clearly reduced as the diborane concentration increases, whereas it increases for increasing amounts of HCl. Although beyond the scope of this work, this effect can be explained as the result of the competing decomposition rates of SiH₄ and GeH₄ at 650°C, as proposed by Lew et al. [32], and the known effects of B₂H₆ and HCl on the growth of Si and Ge NWs. A detailed discussion can be found in *Suppl. section 3.2*. More importantly for the present work, a strong presence of Au is observed in all cases where the diborane partial pressure exceeded ~13 mPa. Therefore, a diborane partial pressure threshold can be established for the growth regime of *Au-free* SiGe NWs. Above 14-18 mPa, the standard growth mechanism is severely altered and strong inclusion of Au is detected.

Figure 3. Compositional XRF (first row), crystallinity TEM (mid row), and HRTEM (lowest row) comparison between SiGe NWs without (left column) and with Au inclusion (right column) originated by a medium (10-13 mPa) versus a high diborane growth conditions (19 mPa) respectively. **a)** Composition analysis of a NW grown with intermediate B_2H_6 partial pressures. The top image shows the SEM view of the very same NW characterized by nano-XRF whose Ge-K and Au-L XRF lines intensities are shown in the middle and bottom figures, respectively. The lower chart shows the longitudinal composition profiles of the NW. **b)** Same XRF analysis as (a) performed over a NW growth with high B_2H_6 partial pressures. No Au NP was found at the tip. **c,d)** Low magnification TEM image of a NW with intermediate (c) and high (d) B_2H_6 partial pressures. **e)** HRTEM imaging of the same NW as (c) at the NW boundary (highlight white square). The inset shows the diffraction pattern obtained with a FFT applied on the lattice. **f)** HRTEM imaging of the same NW as (e) over one high absorbing region (highlight white square). The inset shows the diffraction pattern of the whole image. The nanocluster creates a secondary diffractive peak at higher reciprocal distances in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction.

A deeper analysis by mapping the elemental composition of NWs using nanoscale-resolved X-ray fluorescence, revealed the differences between aligned NWs growth at intermediate B_2H_6 partial pressures (10-13 mPa) and tapered NWs resulting from increased concentration of B_2H_6 (19 mPa). Figure 3a and b depicts a representative example of each case, showing SEM images and co-localized XRF signal mapping of the NWs. Below, the longitudinal concentration profiles of Ge and Au are represented. Figure 3a, corresponding to intermediate diborane partial pressures, shows a constant Ge concentration along the NW longitudinal axis. An intense Au signal at the tip is identified, likely ascribed to the nanoparticle observed in the SEM image. Away from the tip, no evidences of the presence of Au were observed above the detection limit for this particular element (fixed at 75 ppm, see *Suppl. section 3*). Opposite, the analysis of NWs grown at high diborane pressure presented in Figure 3b clearly shows the presence of Au distributed along the whole NW length, suggesting that it has been incorporated in the NW SiGe lattice [33,34]. In all samples analyzed, an increasing Au concentration in the NW growth direction was found. Moreover, the larger diameter observed in these NWs (about 200 nm) decreases while moving away from the base, indicating strong tapering taking place. Finally, a slight variation of the Ge concentration is observed too. This trend is in accordance with reported dependencies of Ge with the diameter in the growth of SiGe NWs [35].

A complementary analysis with TEM and HRTEM (Figure 3c-f) allowed to identify further morphological and structural differences between NWs grown at different diborane partial pressures. As it can be seen in Figure 3c, NWs grown at 10-13 mPa of B_2H_6 showed structural homogeneity throughout their volume. HRTEM images and corresponding diffraction patterns (obtained by Fast Fourier Transform, FFT) revealed an epitaxial growth in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction with a thin (2-3 nm) outer amorphous $Si_{1-x}Ge_xO_2$ native layer. A lattice parameter of $5.48 \pm 0.02 \text{ \AA}$ was calculated from the analysis of the electron diffraction pattern. This value is in good agreement with a Si-Ge alloy with the concentration deduced from the XRF analysis ($x = 0.25 \pm 0.11$). Regarding NWs grown in the high B_2H_6 regime, Figure 3d shows the presence of a large number of highly absorbing regions. These regions are compatible with the presence of heavier atomic species, which would most probably indicate the presence of Au in the host lattice. Selected-area diffraction patterns of these specific regions (dashed ellipse in Figure 3f) revealed the presence of nanocrystalline domains. However, neither the crystal structure nor the lattice parameters obtained are compatible with metallic Au. Indeed, these diffraction patterns (inset of Figure 3f) are still compatible with the SiGe and Si diamond structure, but with a smaller lattice parameter of $4.05 \pm 0.02 \text{ \AA}$ in the NW growth direction ($\langle 111 \rangle$). Additionally, a 3° rotation mismatch is found between both overlapped crystalline lattices.

To further understand the nature of the observed nanoclusters, Tip-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (TERS) maps were acquired on these specific NWs grown at this high B_2H_6 regime. Results are presented in Figure 4. In essence, TERS is a surface-sensitive technique that combines the chemical sensitivity of Raman Spectroscopy and the spatial resolution of AFM (see *Suppl. section 4*). In addition, the TERS signal is expected to be further enhanced in the presence of Au [36]. The lines of the map acquired when the tip is scanning out of the NW presents the three main bands associated to regular $Si_{1-x}Ge_x$ alloy, i.e., Ge-Ge ($\sim 276 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), Si-Ge ($\sim 395 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and Si-Si in SiGe lattice ($\sim 481 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) (see *Figure Suppl. 7* for a detailed discussion). In these regions, the acquired signal comes from the integration of the relatively large laser spot (c.a. $0.5 \mu\text{m}$) hitting the NW bulk, as in a regular confocal Raman experiment. However, when the gold-coated tip is in contact with the NW, this Raman signal is largely boosted. While all the peaks are

amplified, a new doublet peak at ~ 508 and ~ 520 cm^{-1} becomes visible. These have been attributed to strained Si-Si and bulk Si, respectively [37]. The spatial distribution of those peaks (Figure 4c) points to a radial distribution of the strained Si clusters, while more relaxed Si clusters are prone to be concentrated at the NW core. Therefore, it is very likely that the spotted nanoclusters are highly stressed silicon-rich crystal domains. The Au atoms present (as derived in the previous paragraph from the contrast in the HRTEM images) could be distributed at the interfaces between the nanoclusters and the bulk NW, where higher number of defects are expected. This hypothesis is in excellent agreement with: i) the absence of Au crystals as such in obtained HRTEM diffraction patterns, ii) the high correlation in the radial co-localization of both Si nanoclusters density and Au concentration found in thick NWs ($\phi_{NW} \sim 200$ nm) grown at this high B_2H_6 regime depicted in *Figure Suppl. 6*, iii) the local Raman signal enhancement on top of the NWs for the stressed Si-Si bond shown in Figure 4c.

Figure 4. TERS mapping of a NW showing tapering (19 mPa of diborane). a) Comparison between the obtained average Raman spectra inside and outside the NW. b) Topography map of the studied NW. c) Relative intensities TERS map of the shaded Raman bands (red: strained Si-Si; green: relaxed Si-Si). The dashed squares indicate the area where the spectra shown in (a) were averaged.

At the light of the previous results, it can be concluded that the presence of high concentrations of diborane precursor yields the inclusion of Au within the SiGe NWs producing the segregation of silicon-rich nanoclusters inside the lattice. It can be further hypothesized that this segregation efficiently distributes and incorporates Au as impurities through the boundaries between such nanoclusters and NW lattice. Hence, this mechanism is expected to be highly detrimental for the electrical properties of a semiconductor as Au impurities are known to act as mid-energy electron traps, dramatically decreasing the electrical conductivity of the material [38,39]. While further studies should be performed to understand the reasons for the formation of these clusters, this phenomenon could be related to the known fact that diborane gas increases the growth rate as a result of the enhancement of silane decomposition in the gas phase [40,41]. Under this supersaturation regime of the eutectic droplet, the precipitation of Si and Ge can be altered, thus enabling Si to precipitate alone in the form of small clusters [42].

2.2. Thermoelectrical properties

SiGe NWs were integrated in micromachined silicon test platforms (sketched in Figure 5a and b) whose fabrication will be described in the experimental section. Highly tapered SiGe NWs grown under high diborane partial pressures could not be electrically measured due to their high resistivity and non-linearity associated to the presence of contact barriers (see *Figure Suppl. 9*). However, for the case of NWs grown using diborane partial pressure below the threshold of ~ 13 mPa, the electrical behaviour of the studied NW was found to be metallic for temperatures above 350 K (*Figure Suppl. 8*). For lower temperatures, a non-negligible bidirectional (or back-to-back) Schottky barrier of 0.36 eV was found (more details of these characterization can be found in *Suppl. section 5*). The specific suspended NW under study – shown in Figure 5c – presents a diameter of 87 nm, length of 10 μm and distance to the substrate higher than 3 μm (enough to avoid near field radiation effects that could eventually alter the thermal conductivity measurements [43,44]).

Figure 5. **a)** Microdevice structures used for the electrical evaluation of SiGe NWs. **b)** Microsuspended device used to evaluate the Seebeck coefficient and thermoelectric output power of arrays of SiGe NWs. **c)** Tilted SEM image of the studied individual NW integrated into a microtrench. **d)** Optical image showing the device used for the evaluation of the Seebeck coefficient. **e)** Zoom on the microtrenches of the device showing the integrated NW array.

Figure 6 shows the set of electrical, thermal and thermoelectric properties evaluated for this type of NWs (fabricated with the maximum doping level achievable without Au inclusion). Figure 6a shows the electrical conductivity (σ) as a function of temperature. Conductivity values of 76 S/cm were measured close to room temperature, which are far below those of silicon NWs of the same type (diameter and doping level) obtained in previous works. By comparison of the electrical conductivity with the bulk data of similar compositions [45], the doping level of the SiGe NWs is estimated to a range of $(2 - 8) \cdot 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$. This medium doping level could explain the relatively flat trend of σ with temperature, since a remanent

intrinsic behavior at higher temperatures (see *Figure Suppl. 8*) might be in competition with the characteristic metallic-like behavior expected with the increase of electron scattering in the alloyed material [46]. In comparison with the more heavily doped NW tested which do show relevant Au inclusion (see *Figure Suppl. 9*) a much lower effective σ is found (0.7 S/cm). This can be explained if Au impurities are incorporated as substitutional atoms. In such cases, Au is expected to form energy levels close to the valence band, effectively acting as holes deep traps (at around $E_V + 0.4$ eV) [47,48]. Besides, it has been observed that further concentration of Au atoms could even yield to resonant levels in the conduction band [49], which could further disserve the conductivity of the NW. In both studied NW, the doping clearly differs to a greater or lesser extent from the one of the silicon test platforms ($3.5 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) and could explain the presence of a low energy back-to-back Schottky barrier [50,51].

An optical image of the microplatform used for the Seebeck coefficient estimation is presented in Figure 5d. Integrated arrays of NWs are visible as the high reflective yellow parts that joint the suspended microplatform with the bulk. A detailed SEM image is provided in Figure 5e. Seebeck coefficients (S) of similar NWs were measured (see experimental section) and represented as a function of temperature in Figure 6b. Values of around 180 $\mu\text{V/K}$ near room temperature were measured while an increase with temperature is observed, reaching 350 $\mu\text{V/K}$ at 600 K. At this temperature, SiGe NWs surpassed its silicon counterpart previously reported by the authors [31]. Compared to bulk SiGe data from Dismukes et al. [45], the SiGe NW under study showed a reduced S at room temperature, despite having comparatively lower doping levels as deduced from the σ assessment. Because at the scales of the studied NW (87 nm) no alteration of the electronic structure is expected - typically happening for $\phi < 10$ nm - size effects can be discarded as responsible of the observed reduced S [52]. Contrary, the observed reduction is likely related to the suppression of the phonon drag contribution driven by the nanostructuration which doubly affects the thermal conductivity. This effect is not expected to be as important as in the case of pure silicon [53–55] since germanium alloying already induces an important phonon suppression enhancement. However, it might still contribute to this reduction at the low temperature range. Furthermore, similarly to previous reports for silicon NWs [20], the slope of the S evolution is steeper than the bulk counterpart. The reasons of these differences between nanowire and bulk are still under debate but - as discussed above - it cannot be further related to the electron-phonon scattering as this contribution is already vanished [56,57]. Alternatively, it could be related to the effects of Au inclusion as substitutional atoms which are known to yield not only deep traps but also resonant levels [49]. The filling of these levels could be highly sensible to changes in the charge carrier population with temperature expected for the estimated doping level.

Thermal conductivity (κ) values were measured for single SiGe NWs and plotted as a function of temperature in Figure 6c. SiGe NWs achieved thermal conductivities as low as 1.6 W/m·K near room temperature. This represents one order of magnitude reduction compared to silicon NWs of similar type [58] and, at least, a three-fold reduction compared to bulk SiGe of similar composition (according to data of Dismukes et al. [45]). Compared to thermal conductivities previously reported in literature for SiGe NWs, the obtained value is 25 to 50 % lower [59–63]. The obtained κ values were compared with a phonon modelling derived from the Boltzmann transport equation with the relaxation-time approximation [WANG] (the green dashed line in Figure 6c). The model included phonon-phonon scattering, impurity scattering, boundary scattering, and lattice mass mismatch (alloy) scattering. However, while the relatively small core diameter of the studied NW (87 nm) effectively suppressed phonon propagation, even

in a purely diffusive boundary scattering scenario, this factor alone is not sufficient for explaining the low thermal conductivity observed. Therefore, an additional term that accounts for the phonon–surface bond order imperfection scattering was added [64]. This term models the high surface roughness showed by the studied NW, with a rms calculated value of 72 ± 29 nm. Because each protrusion present in the SiGe NWs surface (some of them reaching 100 nm in length and 20 nm in diameter, see *Figure Suppl. 2c-e*) might act as an effective phonon trap, the phonon suppression increases beyond the Casimir limit. With the additional scattering term, the modelling could successfully reproduce the observed κ values.

Figure 6. Summary of thermoelectric properties of the NW analyzed in this work and a comparison to reference literature. **a)** Electrical conductivity (σ). **b)** Seebeck coefficient (S). **c)** Thermal conductivity (κ). **d)** Conductivity ratio (σ/κ). **e)** Power factor (σS^2). **f)** Thermoelectric figure of merit (zT). The blue dots corresponds to this work results while the grey dots and lines represent literature data. The dashed green line in (c) illustrates the obtained estimations of the thermal conductivity using a phonon scattering model [64–67]. Grey continuous line represents values obtained for silicon NWs in previous works [31]. Open diamond shows the value of an undoped $\text{Si}_{0.7}\text{Ge}_{0.3}$ NW of 114.5 nm diameter from previous work [68]. Dashed and dot-dashed lines are bulk values corresponding to doping levels of $3.4 \cdot 10^{19}$ and $8.9 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ respectively from Dismukes et al. [45]. Grey dotted line corresponds to measured values of Kim et al. [69] for undoped $\text{Si}_{0.9}\text{Ge}_{0.1}$ NWs of 97 nm. Black dotted line are Lee et al. [70] values for doped

($9.0 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) $\text{Si}_{0.9}\text{Ge}_{0.1}$ NWs of 160 nm. The upward open triangle corresponds to doped $\text{Si}_{0.6}\text{Ge}_{0.4}$ ($1.2 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) measured by Martinez et al. [71]. The open circle is the average of values from Smith et al. [72] measured over undoped 85-103 nm diameter $\text{Si}_{0.9}\text{Ge}_{0.1}$ NWs.

The impact of this low thermal conductivity can be clearly appreciated in Figure 6d, where the electrical-to-thermal conductivity ratio is presented. The SiGe NW presented a conductivity ratio of $\sigma/\kappa = 5000 \text{ S/W}\cdot\text{K}$, showing that SiGe alloy outperforms their silicon analogous by three times while double the values for heavily doped ($9.0 \cdot 10^{19} \text{ cm}^{-3}$) $\text{Si}_{0.9}\text{Ge}_{0.1}$ NWs of Lee et al. [70]. Therefore, despite showing a comparatively lower power factor ($\sigma \cdot S^2$) than the silicon counterpart due to the reduced σ (Figure 6e), the resulting thermoelectric figure of merit (zT) – presented in Figure 6f – presents an improved performance along the whole temperature range measured compared to integrated Si NWs previously reported in literature, reaching an impressive maximum value of $zT = 0.4$ at 600 K. This enhanced performance at this temperature is the result of a combination of an improved σ/κ and the large increase in the Seebeck coefficient with temperature. Table 2 compares the performance obtained with recent silicon-based nanostructured materials. It is worth highlighting how the presented SiGe NWs are competitive at operational temperatures (600 K) and are - along with the Si NWs of previous works and the work of Elyamny et al. [22] - the only nanomaterials whose zT is currently assessed within the same integration configuration as the one used in the final generator device. Yet, studies improving the zT beyond - as the case of porous Si NWs of Yang et. Al. [73] - proves that even the investigation of those nanomaterials in test conditions are key milestones to incentivize their integration into operative thermoelectric generators despite the challenges some approaches face compared to CVD-VLS.

Table 2. Summary of thermoelectric performance of other silicon based thermoelectric nanomaterials.

Material	Type	κ (W/Km)	zT (300K) (-)	zT (600K) (-)	Reference
Silicon	Dislocated bulk	45	0.045	-	[74]
Silicon	Holey thin film	1.73 ± 0.06	0.4 ± 0.05	-	[75]
Silicon	Porous bulk	7.6	0.25 ± 0.05	-	[76]
Silicon	Porous NW	4.0 ± 0.1	0.31 ± 0.02	0.6 ± 0.07	[73]
Silicon	MACE* NW array	1.8 ± 0.3	0.15	-	[22]
Silicon	Poly nanobulk	0.02 ± 0.001	0.08 ± 0.01	0.2 ± 0.02	[77]
Silicon	Device-integrated NW	15	0.02	0.18	[31]
$\text{MnSi}_{1.74}$	Polybulk	2.65	0.1	0.3	[78]
$\text{Si}_{0.8}\text{Ge}_{0.2}$	Single crystal NW	3.1 ± 1.5	0.04	-	[71]
$\text{Si}_{0.8}\text{Ge}_{0.2}$	Single crystal NW	0.8	0.2	-	[79]
$\text{Si}_{0.6}\text{Ge}_{0.4}$	NP-included polybulk	1.5	0.02	0.2	[80]
$(\text{CrSi}_2)_{0.9}(\text{SiGe})_{0.1}$	NP-included bulk	2.1	0.12	0.27	[81]
$\beta\text{-FeSi-SiGe}$	NP-included bulk	3.3 ± 0.3	0.06 ± 0.03	0.27 ± 0.03	[82]
$\text{Si}_{0.7}\text{Ge}_{0.3}$	Device-integrated NW	1.5	0.06	0.4 ± 0.06	This work

*MACE: Metal Assisted Chemical Etching

2.3. Power harvesting

Due to an always present uncertainty in the quantification of thermoelectrical properties of a nanostructure, one should evaluate its suitability under operation in a real TEG. In this regard, the

excellent thermoelectrical properties obtained for heavily doped SiGe NWs were evaluated here after integration into silicon micromachined devices previously developed for Si NWs [83,84]. Using microfabricated devices sketched in Figure 5b (actual SEM images can be found in the insets of Figure 7b), energy harvesting capabilities were tested locating the devices in contact with a hot surface. Like this, the silicon frame will thermalize with the hot surface, while the suspended platform - properly insulated from the bulk thanks to the low thermal conductivity of the SiGe NWs and the membrane - will be able to hold a slightly lower temperature by releasing heat towards the colder ambient air. Under these circumstances the built-in thermal gradient can be exploited by the integrated NWs arrays thus providing electrical power.

Figure 7a shows the power output of one single suspended microplatform – with a footprint of 2 mm^2 – in contact with a hot surface at temperatures ranging from 50 to 200°C and cooled naturally against the ambient air. A maximum power of 85 nW, with an open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) of 2.27 mV was measured for one single device (top row). The total resistance of the device is fitted to 14.9Ω , which corresponds to an estimated σ value of $57.7 \pm 13 \text{ S/m}$. This estimation is carried out based on the area that NWs populate and a statistical estimation of the density of NWs and their diameter distribution (see *Figure Suppl. 2*). The averaged σ well matches the measured value for the single NW. Furthermore, the obtained power output can be significantly improved either by connecting more platforms in series or parallel configurations [85]. The series configuration - as illustrated in the second row of Figure 7a - can be useful for increasing the output voltage up to 3.6 mV. On the other hand, maximum power can be increased to 110 nW using several platforms in parallel (bottom row), as the total resistance is reduced proportionally. However, in this case, the total output voltage might be lowered since its maximum value will be restricted to the platform showing the lowest value.

Complementary to devices operating under natural convection cooling, the device performance was also evaluated under forced convection conditions. More specifically, the devices were cooled with circulating air with velocities around 1.5 m/s – equivalent to an outdoor breeze or the wind speed felt when walking. As it is shown in Figure 7b, forced convection enables higher open circuit voltages, driven by improved temperature gradients. In particular, the calculated $\Delta T = V_{oc} \cdot S$ can reach 21.9 K compared with the 7.57 K obtained in the natural convection regime. The impact on the power output is also evident as observed in Figure 7b, where the maximum power output for a single platform (top row) raised up to 0.6 μW . Moreover, the series configuration (mid row) allows to reach $V_{oc} = 13.8 \text{ mV}$, which is sufficiently above the minimum level required for an ultra-low voltage DC-DC converter to work ($\sim 9 \text{ mV}$) [86], i.e. opens the way to use this devices to operate systems requiring higher voltages. In the case of the parallel configuration shown in the bottom row of Figure 7b, a maximum power of 1.25 μW is achieved. This value corresponds to a power density of $15.6 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$, compatible with the minimum input power required for ultra-low consumption IoT devices (estimated in $10\text{-}100 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ [87]). The power density reported in this work is indeed comparable state-of-the-art Si and SiGe-based devices, such as the reported by Lee and co. ($\sim 1.9 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ and $27.5 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ using a SiGe and Si CMOS nanoblades respectively) [12,13], Tomita et al. ($\sim 10 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ using CMOS Si NWs) [88], or by Ferrando-Villalba et al. ($\sim 4.1 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ with Si thin films in a similar suspended platform) [18]. Overall, the measured power and voltage outputs combined with the here demonstrated feasibility of integrating several microplatforms per chip proves the suitability of SiGe-based μTENGs for powering autonomous IoT nodes.

Figure 7. Integrated device power curves at temperatures ranging from 50 to 200 °C in different configurations: individual platform (top), series (middle) or parallel (bottom) arrangement). Left column curves **(a)** were measured under free convection regime whereas those on the right column **(b)** were obtained under forced convection regime with air flow of 1.5 m/s. The three configurations of each column share the same axis scale in order to ease the comparison among them. For each configuration each row shows a diagram (left column) and a real SEM image (right-column).

3. Conclusions:

Heavily doped p-type $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x$ NWs with germanium content ranging from $x=0.15$ to 0.4 were successfully produced by VLS-CVD on (111) silicon surfaces at relatively fast growth rates of 100 nm/min. An excellent reproducibility and superior NW lengths (above 15 μm) were reached allowing the integration of such SiGe NWs in silicon micromachined structures for a proper individual characterization. The effect of boron doping level on the functional properties of the nanowires was specifically studied finding a threshold content beyond which, the electrical conductivity and, thus, the TE properties are degraded. Thermoelectric evaluation of optimal SiGe NWs has shown relatively low electrical conductivities of 75

S/m (from 350 to 600K), Seebeck coefficients ranging between 180 to 350 $\mu\text{V}/\text{K}$ (between 350 and 600 K respectively) and a thermal conductivity in the order of 1.3-1.6 $\text{W}/\text{K}\cdot\text{m}$. As a result of this complete characterization of the nanostructure, excellent zT values ranging from 0.06 to 0.4 (from 350 K to 600 K, respectively) were calculated for the p-type SiGe NWs. Overall, the compatibility with silicon microfabrication technologies and the great thermoelectrical properties confirmed that fully integrated μTEG devices based on SiGe nanowires are viable. The integration of such NWs into microfabricated thermoelectric generators was successfully carried out yielding maximum voltage value of 13.8 mV and maximum power density of 15.6 $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ in contact with a hot surface at 200°C (and under forced convection) for series and parallel configurations, respectively. These excellent results anticipate the suitability of such miniaturized TEGs based on SiGe NWs as candidates to power low-power IoT nodes in the next future.

4. Experimental section:

Growth of SiGe NWs: Boron (B) doped bottom-up SiGe NWs were grown by means of the Vapour Liquid Solid (VLS) mechanism within a First Nano EasyTube 3000 Chemical Vapour Deposition (CVD) reactor. The NWs were grown by a CVD-VLS approach following the procedure described elsewhere [89,90] and optimized for their integration into thermoelectric microdevices [91,92]. Gold nanoparticles (Au NPs) were employed as a catalyst for VLS - NW growth. These were deposited following two approaches: i) galvanic displacement [93–95], yielding to highly dense NP patterns within microtrenches of Seebeck characterization devices and ii) electrostatic colloid deposition [96], which led to lower densities and a high control of the diameter of the deposited Au NPs, employed for the single NW σ and κ characterization devices. Details of the galvanic displacement deposition method can be found elsewhere [97]. In this work, a microemulsion parameter of $R = 10$ and a dipping time of $t_{dip} = 7.5$ min were employed in order to achieve an homogeneous deposition of Au within the trenches. For the electrostatic colloid deposition, the approach followed in previous references was employed [92,96]. In this work, a commercial suspension of citrate stabilized 80 nm Au colloids from Sigma Aldrich and poly-L-lysine 0.1% to promote adhesion was employed. The use of a 5% hydrofluoric acid and sonication of the suspension prior to the electrostatic deposition was found to be necessary for preventing agglomeration of colloids. More details about the Au NP deposition methods can be found in *Suppl. section 1*. Samples deposited with the catalyst nanoparticles were introduced in the CVD reactor immediately after a 5 % hydrofluoric acid etch for removing the native oxide layer at the seeded Si surfaces [97]. The CVD conditions optimized for thermoelectric applications and device integration of SiGe NWs are described in Table 1, where the range of diborane (B_2H_6) and hydrochloric acid (HCl) concentrations are also specified.

X-ray fluorescence (XRF): The nano X-ray fluorescence (XRF) data was collected at the beamline ID16B of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility [98]. The X-ray beam (17.5 keV, $\Delta E/E \approx 10^{-2}$) was focused by a pair of KB multilayer mirrors providing a spot of $70 \times 90 \text{ nm}^2$ size with a flux of $2 \cdot 10^{12}$ ph/s. The XRF signal was detected at 15° related to the sample surface using energy disperse silicon drift detectors. NWs were transferred by physical contact from the silicon substrate to X-ray transparent Kapton films. While Ge and Au XRF signals have excellent signal-to-noise ratios for a compositional analysis (above 7.7 in all studied cases), the Si XRF signal was too faint for an accurate evaluation. This was caused by the significant attenuation of the air to the Si XRF K-lines. Therefore, XRF spectra from adjacent pixels (4x4) were added prior to the spectra analysis using the non-linear least-squares fitting code PyMca [99]. This approach

proved useful to increase the signal-to-noise ratio without compromising the longitudinal resolution along the NW axis. Quantitative information on the elemental concentration along the NWs can be extracted following the procedure described in the work of Gómez-Gómez et al. [100] and described in detail in *Suppl. section 2.2*.

Tip-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy: Tip-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (TERS) measurements were performed on a Xplora Nano from HORIBA, using a 632 nm laser and Au-coated OMNI TERS tips. Maps were acquired with a 10 nm/px resolution to build 350x350 nm maps, plotted using a 1.8 px weight average. Acquisition times of 10 seconds per spectra and a 1200 g/mm grating were used.

Microdevice fabrication: Two types of characterization platforms were employed: single NW devices for measuring σ and κ of individual NWs, shown in Figure 5a, and Seebeck (S) and power harvesting (P) devices intended for evaluating S and P in dense NW arrays, illustrated in Figure 5b. Both microdevices were fabricated in cleanroom facilities employing a series of photolithography, metal evaporation and wet and dry etching microfabrication steps [20]. The top layers of these devices were electrically conductive p-type silicon, heavily doped with boron (ensuring a good contact between bulk and grown Si NWs) and featuring tungsten metal contacts on top (allowing no contact resistance with microprobe positioners). Further details on both kind of devices can be found in previous works [31].

Electrical and thermal conductivity measurement: Microdevices specifically designed for electrothermal evaluation of a single NW featured a heavily p-doped silicon layer over an insulating (SiO_2) layer, patterned in an hexagonal shape (see sketch in Figure 5a). In this way, each hexagonal structure is electrically insulated from the rest and can be electrically accessed with microprobes thanks to tungsten contact top-pads. Hence, the microtrenches between adjacent hexagonal structures are designed so that the vertical walls are in the $\langle 111 \rangle$ direction, thus enabling the epitaxial interconnection between them via a single suspended SiGe NW. Hence, NW could be electrically contacted using tungsten microprobes over the microdevice pads. For σ and κ measurements, the devices were loaded into a custom, heated probe stage in vacuum (10^{-2} - 10^{-3} mbar). Electrical measurements were performed using a Keithley 2400 source-meter. The electrical conductivity was calculated from the measured values of resistance (R) and the morphological data of the NW, from room temperature to 620 K. Thermal conductivity measurements were performed with AC measurements, applying the 3- ω method, and using a Stanford Research SR830 Lock-in amplifier for acquiring the third harmonic signal and as the voltage output source [101]. A balance resistor in series with the NW was used for current control (*Figure Suppl. 9*) [102]. Further details on the approaches followed and on the set-up are given in *Suppl. section 6*.

Seebeck coefficient and harvest power output measurement: A second kind of microdevice, consisting of suspended microplatforms, allowed the integration of dense arrays of nanowires with densities between 1 to 5 NWs/ μm . These microplatforms include a heater, which allows to create a forced thermal difference between the bulk and the platform itself (see Figure 5b and *Figure Suppl. 10*). This forced gradient yields a voltage across the NW array such that it can be measured from the external and internal collectors. For these measurements, the devices were loaded within a Linkam HFS720 PB4 gas-tight heating stage in air with the lid closed. The Seebeck coefficient was then evaluated measuring the open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) as a function of the forced thermal gradient (ΔT), from room temperature to 620 K [58]. The harvested power (P) was evaluated by heating the stage and opening the lid, naturally evacuating heat off the

platform. In order to create the stable forced convection flow, a 12 W PC fan was allocated parallel to the heating stage. Details of the approach and the set-up are given in *Suppl. section 7*.

Experimental Author contribution:

Jose M. Sojo Gordillo: conceptualization, investigation, experimental work, data curation, formal analysis, visualization, software, writing – original draft; **Carolina Duque Sierra:** experimental work, writing – review & editing; **Gerard Gadea Diez:** conceptualization, experimental work, writing – review & editing; **Jaime Segura:** experimental work, writing – review & editing; **Valentina Bonino:** data curation; **Juan Carlos Gonzalez-Rosillo:** experimental work, data curation, writing – review & editing; **Marc Nuñez Eroles:** experimental work, data curation; **Denise Estrada-Wiese:** resources; **Marc Salleras:** conceptualization, resources; **Luis Fonseca:** conceptualization, funding acquisition; **Alex Morata:** conceptualization, funding acquisition, writing – review & editing, supervision; **Albert Tarancón:** conceptualization, funding acquisition, review & editing, supervision.

Acknowledgement:

This investigation has been supported by the Spanish Ministry of Education through an FPU grant (**FPU18/01494**), the Generalitat de Catalunya-AGAUR (**2017 SGR 1421**), the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness through the program “Retos de la Sociedad” via the projects **TEC2016-78284-C3-2-R** (AEI/FEDER, EU) “**SIGNAL**” and **TEC2016-78284-C3-1-R** (AEI/FEDER, EU) “**MINAUTO**” and 50% co-financed by the European Union Regional Development Fund (ERDF) within the framework of the ERDF Operational Program of Catalonia 2014–2020 and supported by the University and Research Secretary of the Business and Knowledge Department of the Generalitat de Catalonia in the project **FEM-IoT (001-P-001662)**. This research has also been supported by the Spanish National Research Agency (AEI) through the project **PID2019-110142RB-C21** (AEI/FEDER, EU) “**THERMOLOGICS**”. This research has used the Spanish ICTS Network “**MICRONANOFABS**”, partially funded by FEDER funds through “**MINATEC-PLUS-2**” project **FICTS2019-02-40**. The authors also acknowledge the financial support provided by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Grant Agreement No. **801342** (Tecniospring INDUSTRY), as well as by the Agency for Business Competitiveness of the Government of Catalonia. Finally, the authors acknowledge the European Synchrotron (ESRF) for the beam time allocated on the beamline ID-16B (experiments **MA-4642** and **MA-314**).

Bibliography:

- [1] E. Hittinger, P. Jaramillo, Internet of things: Energy boon or bane?, *Science* (1979). 364 (2019) 326–328. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aau8825>.
- [2] R.J.M. Vullers, R. van Schaijk, I. Doms, C. Van Hoof, R. Mertens, Micropower energy harvesting, *Solid State Electron.* 53 (2009) 684–693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sse.2008.12.011>.
- [3] D. Narducci, Thermoelectric harvesters and the internet of things: technological and economic drivers, *Journal of Physics: Energy.* 1 (2019) 024001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/2515-7655/ab0c3a>.
- [4] N. Garg, R. Garg, Energy harvesting in IoT devices: A survey, *Proceedings of the International Conference on Intelligent Sustainable Systems, ICISS 2017.* (2018) 127–131. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ISS1.2017.8389371>.
- [5] L.E. Bell, Cooling, Heating, Generating Power, and Recovering Waste Heat with Thermoelectric Systems, *Science* (1979). 321 (2008) 1457–1461. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1158899>.
- [6] M. Haras, T. Skotnicki, Thermoelectricity for IoT – A review, *Nano Energy.* 54 (2018) 461–476. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.10.013>.
- [7] A. Tarancón, Powering the IoT revolution with heat, *Nat Electron.* 2 (2019) 270–271. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41928-019-0276-4>.
- [8] C.L. Hsin, M.H. Wu, W.C. Wang, Thermoelectric Devices by Half-Millimeter-Long Silicon Nanowires Arrays, *IEEE Trans Nanotechnol.* 18 (2019) 921–924. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TNANO.2019.2938624>.
- [9] Y. Li, K. Buddharaju, N. Singh, G.Q. Lo, S.J. Lee, Chip-Level Thermoelectric Power Generators Based on High-Density Silicon Nanowire Array Prepared With Top-Down CMOS Technology, *IEEE Electron Device Letters.* 32 (2011) 674–676. <https://doi.org/10.1109/LED.2011.2114634>.
- [10] J. Choi, K. Cho, S. Kim, Flexible Thermoelectric Generators Composed of n-and p-Type Silicon Nanowires Fabricated by Top-Down Method, *Adv Energy Mater.* 7 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.201602138>.
- [11] E. Dimaggio, G. Pennelli, Potentialities of silicon nanowire forests for thermoelectric generation, *Nanotechnology.* 29 (2018) 135401. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-6528/aaa9a2>.
- [12] R. Dhawan, P. Madusanka, G. Hu, J. Debord, T. Tran, K. Maggio, H. Edwards, M. Lee, Si_{0.97}Ge_{0.03} microelectronic thermoelectric generators with high power and voltage densities, *Nat Commun.* 11 (2020) 4362. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-18122-3>.
- [13] G. Hu, H. Edwards, M. Lee, Silicon integrated circuit thermoelectric generators with a high specific power generation capacity, *Nat Electron.* 2 (2019) 300–306. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41928-019-0271-9>.
- [14] Y. Su, J. Lu, D. Villaroman, D. Li, B. Huang, Free-standing planar thermoelectric microrefrigerators based on nano-grained SiGe thin films for on-chip refrigeration, *Nano Energy.* 48 (2018) 202–210. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.03.054>.
- [15] M.M.H. Mahfuz, M. Tomita, S. Hirao, K. Katayama, K. Oda, T. Matsukawa, T. Matsuki, T. Watanabe, Designing a bileg silicon-nanowire thermoelectric generator with cavity-free structure, *Jpn J Appl Phys.* 60 (2021) SBBF07. <https://doi.org/10.35848/1347-4065/abd9d0>.
- [16] S. Koike, R. Yanagisawa, M. Kurosawa, M. Nomura, Design of a planar-type uni-leg SiGe thermoelectric generator, *Jpn J Appl Phys.* 59 (2020) 074003. <https://doi.org/10.35848/1347-4065/ab9d5e>.

- [17] R. Yanagisawa, N. Tsujii, T. Mori, P. Ruther, O. Paul, M. Nomura, Nanostructured planar-type uni-leg Si thermoelectric generators, *Applied Physics Express*. 13 (2020) 095001. <https://doi.org/10.35848/1882-0786/aba5c4>.
- [18] P. Ferrando-Villalba, A.P. Pérez-Marín, L. Abad, G.G. Dalkiranis, A.F. Lopeandia, G. Garcia, J. Rodriguez-Viejo, Measuring Device and Material ZT in a Thin-Film Si-Based Thermoelectric Microgenerator, *Nanomaterials*. 9 (2019) 653. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano9040653>.
- [19] T. Zhan, R. Yamato, S. Hashimoto, M. Tomita, S. Oba, Y. Himeda, K. Mesaki, H. Takezawa, R. Yokogawa, Y. Xu, T. Matsukawa, A. Ogura, Y. Kamakura, T. Watanabe, Miniaturized planar Si-nanowire micro-thermoelectric generator using exuded thermal field for power generation, *Sci Technol Adv Mater*. 19 (2018) 443–453. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14686996.2018.1460177>.
- [20] I. Donmez Noyan, M. Dolcet, M. Salleras, A. Stranz, C. Calaza, G. Gadea, M. Pacios, A. Morata, A. Tarancon, L. Fonseca, All-silicon thermoelectric micro/nanogenerator including a heat exchanger for harvesting applications, *J Power Sources*. 413 (2019) 125–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2018.12.029>.
- [21] I. Donmez Noyan, L. Fonseca, C. Calaza, I. Donmez, Improving the performance of an all-Si based thermoelectric micro / nanogenerator, *Universidad Autonoma de Barcelona*, 2018.
- [22] S. Elyamny, E. Dimaggio, S. Magagna, D. Narducci, G. Pennelli, High Power Thermoelectric Generator Based on Vertical Silicon Nanowires, *Nano Lett*. 20 (2020) 4748–4753. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.0c00227>.
- [23] T. Taniguchi, T. Ishibe, R. Hosoda, Y. Wagatsuma, M.M. Alam, K. Sawano, M. Uenuma, Y. Uraoka, Y. Yamashita, N. Mori, Y. Nakamura, Thermoelectric Si_{1-x}Ge_x and Ge epitaxial films on Si(001) with controlled composition and strain for group IV element-based thermoelectric generators, *Appl Phys Lett*. 117 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0023820>.
- [24] L. Fonseca, I. Donmez-Noyan, M. Dolcet, D. Estrada-Wiese, J. Santander, M. Salleras, G. Gadea, M. Pacios, J. Sojo, A. Morata, A. Tarancon, Transitioning from Si to SiGe Nanowires as Thermoelectric Material in Silicon-Based Microgenerators, *Nanomaterials*. 11 (2021) 517. <https://doi.org/10.3390/nano11020517>.
- [25] L. Pan, K.-K.K. Lew, J.M. Redwing, E.C. Dickey, Effect of diborane on the microstructure of boron-doped silicon nanowires, *J Cryst Growth*. 277 (2005) 428–436. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jcrysgro.2005.01.091>.
- [26] E. Dailey, P. Madras, J. Drucker, Au on vapor-liquid-solid grown Si nanowires: Spreading of liquid AuSi from the catalytic seed, *J Appl Phys*. 108 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3487971>.
- [27] E. Tutuc, S. Guha, J.O. Chu, Morphology of germanium nanowires grown in presence of B₂H₆, *Appl Phys Lett*. 88 (2006) 1–3. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2165089>.
- [28] K.K. Lew, L. Pan, E.C. Dickey, J.M. Redwing, Effect of growth conditions on the composition and structure of Si_{1-x}Ge_x nanowires grown by vapor-liquid-solid growth, *J Mater Res*. 21 (2006) 2876–2881. <https://doi.org/10.1557/jmr.2006.0349>.
- [29] U. Givan, M. Kwiat, F. Patolsky, The Influence of Doping on the Chemical Composition, Morphology and Electrical Properties of Si (1– x) Ge x Nanowires, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. 114 (2010) 4331–4335. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp910934h>.
- [30] A. Potié, T. Baron, L. Latu-Romain, G. Rosaz, B. Salem, L. Montès, P. Gentile, J. Kreisel, H. Roussel, Controlled growth of SiGe nanowires by addition of HCl in the gas phase, *J Appl Phys*. 110 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3610409>.

- [31] G. Gadea Díez, J.M. Sojo Gordillo, M. Pacios Pujadó, M. Salleras, L. Fonseca, A. Morata, A. Tarancón Rubio, Enhanced thermoelectric figure of merit of individual Si nanowires with ultralow contact resistances, *Nano Energy*. 67 (2020) 104191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2019.104191>.
- [32] K.K. Lew, L. Pan, E.C. Dickey, J.M. Redwing, Effect of growth conditions on the composition and structure of Si_{1-x}Ge_x nanowires grown by vapor-liquid-solid growth, *J Mater Res*. 21 (2006) 2876–2881. <https://doi.org/10.1557/jmr.2006.0349>.
- [33] A. Bailly, O. Renault, N. Barrett, L.F. Zagonel, P. Gentile, N. Pauc, F. Dhalluin, T. Baron, A. Chabli, J.C. Cezar, N.B. Brookes, Direct quantification of gold along a single si nanowire, *Nano Lett*. 8 (2008) 3710–3714. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl801952a>.
- [34] E. Dailey, P. Madras, J. Drucker, Au on vapor-liquid-solid grown Si nanowires: Spreading of liquid AuSi from the catalytic seed, *J Appl Phys*. 108 (2010). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3487971>.
- [35] X. Zhang, K. Lew, P. Nimmatoori, J.M. Redwing, E.C. Dickey, Diameter-Dependent Composition of Vapor–Liquid–Solid Grown Si_{1-x}Ge_x Nanowires, *Nano Lett*. 7 (2007) 3241–3245. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl071132u>.
- [36] Z. Yang, J. Aizpurua, H. Xu, Electromagnetic field enhancement in TERS configurations, *Journal of Raman Spectroscopy*. 40 (2009) 1343–1348. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jrs.2429>.
- [37] T.A. Langdo, M.T. Currie, A. Lochtefeld, R. Hammond, J.A. Carlin, M. Erdtmann, G. Braithwaite, V.K. Yang, C.J. Vineis, H. Badawi, M.T. Bulsara, SiGe-free strained Si on insulator by wafer bonding and layer transfer, *Appl Phys Lett*. 82 (2003) 4256–4258. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1581371>.
- [38] A. Jain, S.P. Ong, G. Hautier, W. Chen, W.D. Richards, S. Dacek, S. Cholia, D. Gunter, D. Skinner, G. Ceder, K.A. Persson, Commentary: The Materials Project: A materials genome approach to accelerating materials innovation, *APL Mater*. 1 (2013) 011002. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4812323>.
- [39] S.P. Ong, W.D. Richards, A. Jain, G. Hautier, M. Kocher, S. Cholia, D. Gunter, V.L. Chevrier, K.A. Persson, G. Ceder, Python Materials Genomics (pymatgen): A robust, open-source python library for materials analysis, *Comput Mater Sci*. 68 (2013) 314–319. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.commatsci.2012.10.028>.
- [40] H. Schmid, M.T. Björk, J. Knoch, S. Karg, H. Riel, W. Riess, Doping limits of grown in situ doped silicon nanowires using phosphine, *Nano Lett*. 9 (2009) 173–177. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl802739v>.
- [41] U. Givan, M. Kwiat, F. Patolsky, The Influence of Doping on the Chemical Composition, Morphology and Electrical Properties of Si(1-x)Ge_x Nanowires, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C*. 114 (2010) 4331–4335. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp910934h>.
- [42] W.B. Wang, M. Kambara, A molecular dynamics simulation of inhomogeneous silicon-germanium nucleation from supersaturated vapor mixtures, *AIP Adv*. 11 (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0049820>.
- [43] C.J. Fu, Z.M. Zhang, Nanoscale radiation heat transfer for silicon at different doping levels, *Int J Heat Mass Transf*. 49 (2006) 1703–1718. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2005.09.037>.
- [44] L.Y. Carrillo, Y. Bayazitoglu, Nanorod near-field radiative heat exchange analysis, *J Quant Spectrosc Radiat Transf*. 112 (2011) 412–419. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2010.10.011>.
- [45] J.P. Dismukes, L. Ekstrom, E.F. Steigmeier, I. Kudman, D.S. Beers, Thermal and Electrical Properties of Heavily Doped GeSi Alloys up to 1300 ° K, *J. Appl. Phys*. 2899 (1964) 2899–2907. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.1713126>.

- [46] J. Singh, *Physics of Semiconductors and Their Heterostructures*, McGraw Hill, New York, NY, 1996.
- [47] M. Schulz, *Applied Physics Determination of Deep Trap Levels in Silicon Using Ion-Implantation and CV-Measurements*, Springer-Verlag, 1974.
- [48] A.J. Tavendale, S.J. Pearton, Deep level, quenched-in defects in silicon doped with gold, silver, iron, copper or nickel, 1983. <http://iopscience.iop.org/0022-3719/16/9/011>.
- [49] S. Sakane, T. Ishibe, K. Mizuta, T. Fujita, Y. Kiyofuji, J.I. Ohe, E. Kobayashi, Y. Nakamura, Anomalous enhancement of thermoelectric power factor by thermal management with resonant level effect, *J Mater Chem A Mater.* 9 (2021) 4851–4857. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0ta08683e>.
- [50] R.T. Tung, The physics and chemistry of the Schottky barrier height, *Appl Phys Rev.* 1 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4858400>.
- [51] J.L. Barreda, T.D. Keiper, M. Zhang, P. Xiong, Multiple Schottky Barrier-Limited Field-Effect Transistors on a Single Silicon Nanowire with an Intrinsic Doping Gradient, *ACS Appl Mater Interfaces.* 9 (2017) 12046–12053. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsami.7b00144>.
- [52] M.S. Dresselhaus, G. Dresselhaus, S. Cronin, A.G.S. Filho, *Solid State Properties: From Bulk to Nano*, Springer-Verlag Berlin Heidelberg, 2018.
- [53] J. Sadhu, H. Tian, J. Ma, B. Azeredo, J. Kim, K. Balasundaram, C. Zhang, X. Li, P.M. Ferreira, S. Sinha, Quenched Phonon Drag in Silicon Nanowires Reveals Significant Effect in the Bulk at Room Temperature, *Nano Lett.* 15 (2015) 3159–3165. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.5b00267>.
- [54] S. Elyamny, E. Dimaggio, G. Pennelli, Seebeck coefficient of silicon nanowire forests doped by thermal diffusion, *Beilstein Journal of Nanotechnology.* 11 (2020) 1707–1713. <https://doi.org/10.3762/bjnano.11.153>.
- [55] J.M. Sojo-Gordillo, D. Estrada-Wiese, C. Duque-Sierra, G. Gadea-Díez, M. Salleras, L. Fonseca, A. Morata, A. Tarancón, Tuning the Thermoelectric Properties of Boron-Doped Silicon Nanowires Integrated into a Micro-Harvester, *Adv Mater Technol.* 7 (2022) 2101715. <https://doi.org/10.1002/admt.202101715>.
- [56] G. Joshi, H. Lee, Y. Lan, X. Wang, G. Zhu, D. Wang, R.W. Gould, D.C. Cuff, M.Y. Tang, M.S. Dresselhaus, G. Chen, Z. Ren, Enhanced thermoelectric figure-of-merit in nanostructured p-type silicon germanium bulk alloys, *Nano Lett.* 8 (2008) 4670–4674. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl8026795>.
- [57] S.I. Yi, C. Yu, Modeling of thermoelectric properties of SiGe alloy nanowires and estimation of the best design parameters for high figure-of-merits, *J Appl Phys.* 117 (2015). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4906226>.
- [58] G. Gadea Díez, J.M. Sojo Gordillo, M. Pacios Pujadó, M. Salleras, L. Fonseca, A. Morata, A. Tarancón Rubio, Enhanced thermoelectric figure of merit of individual Si nanowires with ultralow contact resistances, *Nano Energy.* 67 (2020) 104191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2019.104191>.
- [59] K.M. Lee, S.K. Lee, T.Y. Choi, Highly enhanced thermoelectric figure of merit of a β -SiC nanowire with a nanoelectromechanical measurement approach, *Appl Phys A Mater Sci Process.* 106 (2012) 955–960. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-011-6718-0>.
- [60] J.M. Sojo Gordillo, G. Gadea Díez, M. Pacios Pujadó, M. Salleras, D. Estrada-Wiese, M. Dolcet, L. Fonseca, A. Morata, A. Tarancón, Thermal conductivity of individual Si and SiGe epitaxially integrated NWs by scanning thermal microscopy, *Nanoscale.* 13 (2021) 7252–7265. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1NR00344E>.

- [61] J.A. Martinez, P.P. Provencio, S.T. Picraux, J.P. Sullivan, B.S. Swartzentruber, Enhanced thermoelectric figure of merit in SiGe alloy nanowires by boundary and hole-phonon scattering, *J Appl Phys.* 110 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3647575>.
- [62] H. Kim, I. Kim, H. Choi, W. Kim, Thermal conductivities of Si_{1-x}Ge_x nanowires with different germanium concentrations and diameters, *Appl Phys Lett.* 96 (2010) 233106. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3443707>.
- [63] B. Smith, G. Fleming, K.D. Parrish, F. Wen, E. Fleming, K. Jarvis, E. Tutuc, A.J.H. Mcgaughey, L. Shi, Mean Free Path Suppression of Low-Frequency Phonons in SiGe Nanowires, *Nano Lett.* 20 (2020) 8384–8391. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.0c03590>.
- [64] H.-Y. Yang, Y.-L. Chen, W.-X. Zhou, G.-F. Xie, N. Xu, Ultra-low thermal conductivity of roughened silicon nanowires: Role of phonon-surface bond order imperfection scattering, *Chinese Physics B.* (2020) 0–14. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1674-1056/ab99af>.
- [65] Z. Wang, N. Mingo, Diameter dependence of SiGe nanowire thermal conductivity, *Appl Phys Lett.* 97 (2010) 101903. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3486171>.
- [66] A.J. Minnich, H. Lee, X.W. Wang, G. Joshi, M.S. Dresselhaus, Z.F. Ren, G. Chen, D. Vashaee, Modeling study of thermoelectric SiGe nanocomposites, *Phys Rev B.* 80 (2009) 155327. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.80.155327>.
- [67] Y. Ohishi, J. Xie, Y. Miyazaki, Y. Aikebaier, H. Muta, K. Kurosaki, S. Yamanaka, N. Uchida, T. Tada, Thermoelectric properties of heavily boron- and phosphorus-doped silicon, *Jpn J Appl Phys.* 54 (2015) 071301. <https://doi.org/10.7567/JJAP.54.071301>.
- [68] J.M. Sojo Gordillo, G. Gadea Diez, M. Pacios Pujadó, M. Salleras, D. Estrada-Wiese, M. Dolcet, L. Fonseca, A. Morata, A. Tarancón, Thermal conductivity of individual Si and SiGe epitaxially integrated NWs by scanning thermal microscopy, *Nanoscale.* 13 (2021) 7252–7265. <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1NR00344E>.
- [69] H. Kim, I. Kim, H. Choi, W. Kim, Thermal conductivities of Si_{1-x}Ge_x nanowires with different germanium concentrations and diameters, *Appl Phys Lett.* 96 (2010) 233106. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3443707>.
- [70] E.K. Lee, L. Yin, Y. Lee, J.W. Lee, S.J. Lee, J. Lee, S.N. Cha, D. Whang, G.S. Hwang, K. Hippalgaonkar, A. Majumdar, C. Yu, B.L. Choi, J.M. Kim, K. Kim, Large thermoelectric figure-of-merits from SiGe nanowires by simultaneously measuring electrical and thermal transport properties, *Nano Lett.* 12 (2012) 2918–2923. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl300587u>.
- [71] J.A. Martinez, P.P. Provencio, S.T. Picraux, J.P. Sullivan, B.S. Swartzentruber, Enhanced thermoelectric figure of merit in SiGe alloy nanowires by boundary and hole-phonon scattering, *J Appl Phys.* 110 (2011). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3647575>.
- [72] B. Smith, G. Fleming, K.D. Parrish, F. Wen, E. Fleming, K. Jarvis, E. Tutuc, A.J.H. Mcgaughey, L. Shi, Mean Free Path Suppression of Low-Frequency Phonons in SiGe Nanowires, *Nano Lett.* 20 (2020) 8384–8391. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.nanolett.0c03590>.
- [73] L. Yang, D. Huh, R. Ning, V. Rapp, Y. Zeng, Y. Liu, S. Ju, Y. Tao, Y. Jiang, J. Beak, J. Leem, S. Kaur, H. Lee, X. Zheng, R.S. Prasher, High thermoelectric figure of merit of porous Si nanowires from 300 to 700 K, *Nat Commun.* 12 (2021) 3926. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-24208-3>.
- [74] N.S. Bennett, D. Byrne, A. Cowley, N. Neophytou, Dislocation loops as a mechanism for thermoelectric power factor enhancement in silicon nano-layers, *Appl Phys Lett.* 109 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4966686>.

- [75] J. Tang, H.T. Wang, D.H. Lee, M. Fardy, Z. Huo, T.P. Russell, P. Yang, Holey silicon as an efficient thermoelectric material, *Nano Lett.* 10 (2010) 4279–4283. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl102931z>.
- [76] J. de Boor, D.S. Kim, X. Ao, M. Becker, N.F. Hinsche, I. Mertig, P. Zahn, V. Schmidt, Thermoelectric properties of porous silicon, *Appl Phys A Mater Sci Process.* 107 (2012) 789–794. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00339-012-6879-5>.
- [77] A. Morata, M. Pacios, G. Gadea, C. Flox, D. Cadavid, A. Cabot, A. Tarancón, Large-area and adaptable electrospun silicon-based thermoelectric nanomaterials with high energy conversion efficiencies, *Nat Commun.* 9 (2018) 4759. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-018-07208-8>.
- [78] S. le Tonquesse, L. Joanny, Q. Guo, E. Elkaim, V. Demange, D. Berthebaud, T. Mori, M. Pasturel, C. Prestipino, Influence of Stoichiometry and Aging at Operating Temperature on Thermoelectric Higher Manganese Silicides, *Chemistry of Materials.* 32 (2020) 10601–10609. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.chemmater.0c03714>.
- [79] E.K. Lee, L. Yin, Y. Lee, J.W. Lee, S.J. Lee, J. Lee, S.N. Cha, D. Whang, G.S. Hwang, K. Hippalgaonkar, A. Majumdar, C. Yu, B.L. Choi, J.M. Kim, K. Kim, Large thermoelectric figure-of-merits from SiGe nanowires by simultaneously measuring electrical and thermal transport properties, *Nano Lett.* 12 (2012) 2918–2923. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl300587u>.
- [80] K. Xie, M.C. Gupta, Thermoelectric properties of SiGe thin films prepared by laser sintering of nanograin powders, *J Alloys Compd.* 820 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2019.153182>.
- [81] N.K. Upadhyay, L.A. Kumaraswamidhas, B. Gahtori, S. Bathula, S. Muthiah, R. Shyam, N.S. Chauhan, R. Bhardwaj, A. Dhar, Enhancement in thermoelectric performance of bulk CrSi₂ dispersed with nanostructured SiGe nanoinclusions, *J Alloys Compd.* 765 (2018) 412–417. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2018.06.175>.
- [82] N. Liu, S.E. Rezaei, W.A. Jensen, S. Song, Z. Ren, K. Esfarjani, M. Zebarjadi, J.A. Floro, Improved Thermoelectric Performance of Eco-Friendly β -FeSi₂-SiGe Nanocomposite via Synergistic Hierarchical Structuring, Phase Percolation, and Selective Doping, *Adv Funct Mater.* 29 (2019) 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adfm.201903157>.
- [83] I. Donmez Noyan, M. Dolcet, M. Salleras, A. Stranz, C. Calaza, G. Gadea, M. Pacios Pujadó, Á. Morata, A. Tarancón, L. Fonseca, M. Pacios, A. Morata, A. Tarancon, L. Fonseca, All-silicon thermoelectric micro/nanogenerator including a heat exchanger for harvesting applications, *J Power Sources.* 413 (2019) 125–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2018.12.029>.
- [84] I. Donmez Noyan, G. Gadea, M. Salleras, M. Pacios, C. Calaza, A. Stranz, M. Dolcet, A. Morata, A. Tarancon, L. Fonseca, SiGe nanowire arrays based thermoelectric microgenerator, *Nano Energy.* 57 (2019) 492–499. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.12.050>.
- [85] F. Morais, P. Carvalhaes-Dias, L. Duarte, A. Spengler, K. De Paiva, T. Martins, A. Cabot, J.S. Dias, J. Siqueira Dias, Optimization of the TEGs Configuration (Series/Parallel) in Energy Harvesting Systems with Low-Voltage Thermoelectric Generators Connected to Ultra-Low Voltage DC–DC Converters, *Energies (Basel).* 13 (2020) 2297. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13092297>.
- [86] L. Colalongo, D.I. Leu, A. Richelli, Zs. Kovacs, Ultra-Low Voltage Push-Pull Converter for Micro Energy Harvesting, *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems II: Express Briefs.* PP (2020) 1–1. <https://doi.org/10.1109/tcsii.2020.2965551>.
- [87] M. Haras, T. Skotnicki, Thermoelectricity for IoT – a review, *Nano Energy.* (2018). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2018.10.013>.

- [88] M. Tomita, S. Oba, Y. Himeda, R. Yamato, K. Shima, T. Kumada, M. Xu, H. Takezawa, K. Mesaki, K. Tsuda, S. Hashimoto, T. Zhan, H. Zhang, Y. Kamakura, Y. Suzuki, H. Inokawa, H. Ikeda, T. Matsukawa, T. Matsuki, T. Watanabe, Modeling, Simulation, Fabrication, and Characterization of a 10- $\mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$ Class Si-Nanowire Thermoelectric Generator for IoT Applications, *IEEE Trans Electron Devices*. 65 (2018) 5180–5188. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TED.2018.2867845>.
- [89] M.S. Islam, S. Sharma, T.I. Kamins, R.S. Williams, Ultrahigh-density silicon nanobridges formed between two vertical silicon surfaces, *Nanotechnology*. 15 (2004). <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-4484/15/5/L01>.
- [90] D. Dávila, A. Tarancón, C. Calaza, M. Salleras, M. Fernández-Regúlez, A. San Paulo, L. Fonseca, Monolithically integrated thermoelectric energy harvester based on silicon nanowire arrays for powering micro/nanodevices, *Nano Energy*. 1 (2012) 812–819. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2012.06.006>.
- [91] G. Gadea, Á. Morata, J.D. Santos, D. Dávila, C. Calaza, M. Salleras, L. Fonseca, A. Tarancón, A. Morata, J.D. Santos, D. Dávila, C. Calaza, M. Salleras, L. Fonseca, A. Tarancón, Towards a full integration of vertically aligned silicon nanowires in MEMS using silane as a precursor, *Nanotechnology*. 26 (2015) 195302. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-4484/26/19/195302>.
- [92] G. Gadea, Integration of Si/Si-Ge nanostructures in micro-thermoelectric generators, Universidad de Barcelona, 2017.
- [93] L. Magagnin, V. Bertani, P.L. Cavallotti, R. Maboudian, C. Carraro, Selective deposition of gold nanoclusters on silicon by a galvanic displacement process, *Microelectron Eng*. 64 (2002) 479–485. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-9317\(02\)00824-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0167-9317(02)00824-9).
- [94] D. Gao, R. He, C. Carraro, R.T. Howe, P. Yang, R. Maboudian, Selective growth of Si nanowire arrays via galvanic displacement processes in water-in-oil microemulsions, *J Am Chem Soc*. 127 (2005) 4574–4575. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ja043645y>.
- [95] G. Gadea, A. Morata, J.D. Santos, D. Dávila, C. Calaza, M. Salleras, L.L.L. Fonseca, A. Tarancón, Á. Morata, J.D. Santos, D. Dávila, C. Calaza, M. Salleras, L.L.L. Fonseca, A. Tarancón, A. Morata, J.D. Santos, D. Dávila, C. Calaza, M. Salleras, L.L.L. Fonseca, A. Tarancón, Towards a full integration of vertically aligned silicon nanowires in MEMS using silane as a precursor, *Nanotechnology*. 26 (2015) 195302. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-4484/26/19/195302>.
- [96] A.I. Hochbaum, R. Fan, R. He, P. Yang, Controlled growth of Si nanowire arrays for device integration, *Nano Lett*. 5 (2005) 457–460. <https://doi.org/10.1021/nl047990x>.
- [97] G. Gadea, A. Morata, J.D. Santos, D. Dávila, C. Calaza, M. Salleras, L. Fonseca, A. Tarancón, A. Morata, J.D. Santos, D. Dávila, C. Calaza, M. Salleras, L. Fonseca, A. Tarancón, Towards a full integration of vertically aligned silicon nanowires in MEMS using silane as a precursor, *Nanotechnology*. 26 (2015) 195302. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-4484/26/19/195302>.
- [98] G. Martínez-Criado, J. Villanova, R. Tucoulou, D. Salomon, J.P. Suuronen, S. Laboure, C. Guilloud, V. Valls, R. Barrett, E. Gagliardini, Y. Dabin, R. Baker, S. Bohic, C. Cohen, J. Morse, ID16B: A hard X-ray nanoprobe beamline at the ESRF for nano-analysis, *J Synchrotron Radiat*. 23 (2016) 344–352. <https://doi.org/10.1107/S1600577515019839>.
- [99] V.A. Solé, E. Papillon, M. Cotte, Ph. Walter, J. Susini, A multiplatform code for the analysis of energy-dispersive X-ray fluorescence spectra, *Spectrochim Acta Part B At Spectrosc*. 62 (2007) 63–68. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sab.2006.12.002>.
- [100] M. Gómez-Gómez, N. Garro, J. Segura-Ruiz, G. Martínez-Criado, A. Cantarero, H.T. Mengistu, A. García-Cristóbal, S. Murcia-Mascarós, C. Denker, J. Malindretos, A. Rizzi,

- Spontaneous core-shell elemental distribution in In-rich $\text{In}_x\text{Ga}_{1-x}\text{N}$ nanowires grown by molecular beam epitaxy, *Nanotechnology*. 25 (2014). <https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-4484/25/7/075705>.
- [101] G. Pennelli, E. Dimaggio, M. Macucci, Note: Improvement of the 3ω thermal conductivity measurement technique for its application at the nanoscale, *Review of Scientific Instruments*. 89 (2018) 016104. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.5008807>.
- [102] C. Xing, C. Jensen, T. Munro, B. White, H. Ban, M. Chirtoc, Thermal property characterization of fine fibers by the 3-omega technique, *Appl Therm Eng*. 71 (2014) 589–595. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2014.06.022>.

Superior thermoelectric performance of SiGe NWs epitaxially integrated into thermal micro-harvesters

Supplementary Information

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1. Seeding methods, NW distribution, and surface roughness

As it was described in the experimental section, the growth of bottom-up VLS-CVD NWs requires a prior deposition of Au nanoparticles over the substrate which ultimately act as the catalyst seeds for the NW growth. Figure Suppl. 1 illustrates both methods.

Figure Suppl. 1. Scheme of the two methods employed for deposition Au nanoparticles serving as seeds for the catalysed VLS growth of NWs. a) Galvanic displacement method employed to selectively deposit dense arrays of NPs over exposed Si surfaces. b) Electrostatic deposition of Au colloids used to unselectively deposit highly controlled.

For the case of the growth of dense NW arrays, the assessment of both diameter and density distribution results useful to the quantitative study on differences between growths. Yet, more

importantly, it can be used also to deduce an average electrical conductivity of the material from the measured electrical resistance R_e , knowing that:

$$\sigma = \frac{4 R_e}{\pi A \rho_{NW} \phi_{NW}^2 L N_T} \quad \text{S. Eq. 1}$$

Where ρ_{NW} is the average density of the NWs, ϕ_{NW} is the average NW diameter and A , L , N_T are the growth area, NW length and number of trenches in series respectively, defined by the design specification of the microdevices used in this work (see Table Suppl. 1). Both ρ_{NW} and ϕ_{NW} were estimated using the image processing software ImageJ. As Figure Suppl. 2a-b shows, the diameter distribution can be described using a normal distribution, whereas the average NW density analysed from several SEM top views allowed to estimate the NW density too.

For the case of individual integrated NW, the roughness was estimated analysing the surface profile obtained from high magnification SEM imaging of the NW (Figure Suppl. 2c-d). The profile was obtained using a high contrast filter in an image processing toll (Image J) and then digitalized into a list of points with radial and longitudinal coordinates. The histogram of the radial coordinate of all the points mapped in the profile allows to fit a gaussian distribution (Figure Suppl. 2e). The obtained mean of such fit corresponds to the rms roughness parameter.

Figure Suppl. 2. a) Diameter distribution of the dense NW arrays used in this work for the Seebeck coefficient evaluation and the power harvesting. b) NW density estimation from top view SEM images of the dense array of NWs. c) SEM imaging of the single suspended NW measured. d) Profile of the surface. e) Histogram showing the roughness density distribution of the NW surface. Used to compute the roughness rms value as the mean of the Gaussian fits.

Table Suppl. 1. Geometrical parameters of the thermoelectric device.

Cross section area - A	NW Length - L	Number of trenches N_T	NW diameter - ϕ_{NW}	NW density - ρ_{NW}
45000 μm^2	15 μm	4	52.1 \pm 10 nm	7.29 \pm 1.53 NW/ μm^2

2. X-ray fluorescence measurements:

2.1. XRF quantification:

Quantitative information on the elemental concentration along the NWs can be extracted from XRF spectra thanks to the relationship between the intensity of each elemental fluorescence line, I_i , and its concentration, C_i , as describes *S. Eq. 2*. This equation is obtained for a flat sample excited by a monochromatic incoming X-ray beam. Enhancement effects due to additional excitation of the element of interest by the characteristic radiation of other elements in the sample are therefore neglected (an assumption that is valid for thin samples).

$$I_i = I_0 \gamma_i C_i \int_0^t \exp\left(-\left[\frac{\mu(h\nu)}{\sin \theta_1} + \frac{\mu(E_i)}{\sin \theta_2}\right]y\right) dy \quad \text{S. Eq. 2}$$

where I_0 is the intensity of the incoming beam and γ_i accounts for the fluorescence yield, solid angle, and detection efficiency. The attenuation due to the sample thickness, t , is given by the integral, where μ is the total mass absorption coefficient at the energy of the fluorescence, E_i , and the excitation, $h\nu$, and θ_i are the excitation and detection angles relative to the sample surface. As the total mass absorption coefficient of the alloy is given by $\mu = \sum_i C_i \mu_i$, *S. Eq. 2* can be solved iteratively by imposing stoichiometric conditions ($C_i = 1$). Special attention has been paid to the variation of the sample thickness along the NW radius. Considering that $\mu t \ll 1$ for the experimental conditions employed herein (i.e. excitation and detection angles, diameters and alloy compositions) the thin sample approximation can be assumed [1]. Therefore, equation can be simplified to:

$$I_i \cong I_0 \gamma_i C_i t \quad \text{S. Eq. 3}$$

As described in the experimental section, XRF maps of all samples were taken with a beam spot of 55 nm, yielding the corresponding map resolutions. An example of a raw count mapping showing the full resolution can be seen in Figure Suppl. 4. However, due to the large size of the NW measurements, the integration per pixel was set to 500-1000 ms in order to make possible the measurement within a reasonable time of several hours. This low time added to the significant attenuation of the Si-K lines induced by the air between the sample and the detector (1.5 cm approx.), reduces the sensitivity to detect Si. For this reason, eight adjacent pixels were binned to increase the sensitivity at the expense of spatial resolution.

However, the adjacent pixel addition approach was not possible in all experimental runs. Without the silicon contribution, gold concentration could not be quantified alone directly using *S. Eq. 2* or *S. Eq. 3*. In order to overcome this issue, a later EDX analysis under a SEM was used to obtain a good estimate of the Si/Ge ratio. Then, this germanium composition values were compared with the relation of intensities of the gold and germanium lines - both with energies higher than 9 keV

- and thus not attenuated by few centimetres of air -, so that gold concentration could be estimated assuming that $C_{Si} + C_{Ge} + C_{Au} \approx C_{Si} + C_{Ge} = 1$ and thus:

$$C_{Au} = C_{Ge} \frac{I_{Ge-K} \cdot \gamma_{Ge-K}}{I_{Au-L_i} \cdot \gamma_{Au-L_i}} \quad S. Eq. 4$$

2.2. Limit of detection:

The detection limit for Au was computed by simulating in PyMCA the signal produced by a layer of 100 nm – i.e. in the order of magnitude of the diameter of the studied NW and thin enough to consider self-absorption negligible – for a SiGe matrix with similar Si/Ge ratios as those found in the studied samples. In this way, several spectra of the material with varying contents of Au were simulated. As it is illustrated in Figure Suppl. 3, the intersection of the signal to noise ratio as a function of the Au concentration against $y = 3$ and $y = 10$ determine the Limit of Detection (LOD) and the Limit of Quantification (LOQ) respectively. In this case, those values were found to be 75 and 1641 ppm respectively.

Figure Suppl. 3. a) Example showing 2 simulated spectra with different concentrations of Au over the fitted background of experimental measurements. b) Chart showing the computed normalized signal respect to background noise at 11.44 keV (Au emission line L2M4) as a function of the Au concentration.

2.3. Additional samples acquired:

A minimum of 2 NWs were examined for each sample, all samples used are summarized in Table Suppl. 2. Figure Suppl. 4 shows the SEM images, AFM topography, Ge-K and Au-L2 emission lines and the Au computed concentration using *S. Eq. 3*. These measurements corresponds to samples A_x (HCl:SiH₄ = 1.5). The Si/Ge ratio in these samples was extracted from further EDX analysis of the same NWs. It was found to be $x = 0.212$ and $x = 0.192$ for samples A₁ and A₂ respectively. The rest of the measurements (samples B_x with HCl:SiH₄ = 1.75) were carried out with increased integration time per pixel, so direct quantification of elements could be undergone directly from the XRF spectra (using *S. Eq. 2*). Figure Suppl. 5 shows the SEM images, raw counts XRF signal and derived concentration maps obtained for several NWs from all the analysed samples of this work. All these data were employed in the elaboration the study described in Figure 3.

Table Suppl. 2. Summary of growth conditions used in this work. For all cases the rest of the conditions are stated in Table 1.

Sample	Study	[B ₂ H ₆] (mPa)	HCl:SiH ₄ ratio	Gold inclusion
A1	XRF - TEM	9.2	1.5	No
A2	XRF	19	1.5	Yes
B1	XRF	4.9	1.75	No
B2	XRF - Power harvest	13	1.75	No
B3	XRF - TEM	19	1.75	Yes
C1	Electrothermal	9.2	1.75	No*
C2	Seebeck	9.6	1.75	No*
C3	Electrothermal	19	1.75	Yes*

* Not directly measured

Figure Suppl. 4. Additional XRF maps of studied samples. In descending order, SEM image of the NW, AFM scans, Ge-K and Au-L2 line counts maps and calculated concentrations for Au respectively. Concentration was in this case calculated using a Si-Ge ratio computed from EDX measurements. Images shows NW samples A_x (HCl:SiH₄ = 1.5) with different used diborane concentrations: a) 9.2mPa b) 19 mPa.

Figure Suppl. 5. Additional XRF maps of studied samples. In descending order, SEM image of the NW, raw counts of the acquired map and obtained concentrations for Si, Ge and Au respectively. Concentration maps resolution is decreased as a result of adjacent pixel addition post-process intended for improving the spectral resolution. Images shows NW of samples B_x (HCl:SiH₄ = 1.75) with different used diborane concentrations: a) 4.9mPa b) 13mPa c) 19mPa.

3. Composition trend hypothesis:

3.1. Gold presence in tapered NWs:

In section 3.1, a discussion about the nature of the gold presence within the NW is carried out. HRTEM images (Figure 4c-d) already showed the presence of darker zones distributed inside the NW lattice corresponding to the presence of heavier elements. This, added to the fact that no electrical measurements (too high barrier-like behavior) could be performed over the NWs of these samples points out to the hypothesis that Au presence is tightly related to the presence of nanoclusters within the NW lattice. This section adds further evidence by comparing the radial distribution of gold with the radial density of nanoclusters, as depicts Figure Suppl. 6. As it can be

appreciated, for thick NW, the X-ray beam spatial distribution was sharp enough (~ 75 nm) to reveal two maxima in the Au-L signal profile typical of a core-shell structure. This distribution is not observed in other inspected elements (Si, Ge). Similarly, when the density of nanoclusters is counted using the HRTEM image of a NW growth under the same conditions, a clear increase in the number of nanoclusters can be appreciated close to the NW surface respect to the core, in good agreement with the XRF results.

Figure Suppl. 6. Analysis of the Au radial segregation. a) SEM and XRF element count maps (in decreasing order Si, Ge and Au) of one NW of sample B₃ (19 mPa of B₂H₆) b) Radial elemental distribution of the same NW. Five pixels were integrated in the longitudinal axis to improve spectrum accuracy. c) HRTEM imaging of a similar NW of sample B₃. The NW is divided in 7 segments in order to compute the nanocluster density. d) Histogram of the nanocluster density.

3.2. Germanium trend:

In section 3.1 some hypothesis regarding the Germanium composition dependence with diborane and HCl observed in Figure 3 are stated. These effects can be understood if one considers the resulting Ge concentration as the result of the competing decomposition rates of SiH₄ and GeH₄ proposed by Lew et. Al. [2]. The presence of diborane is known to enhance the dissociation of both SiH₄ and GeH₄ whereas the HCl is known to act inversely. However, due to the overall faster dissociation of GeH₄ at the growth temperatures (650 °C), the growth conditions chosen are such that SiH₄ is in clear excess while GeH₄ might be limited. Under this assumption, the presence of B₂H₆ can explain an increase in the Si inclusion while all the available Ge might be already incorporated. Inversely, the presence of HCl impedes both gases dissociation, but since GeH₄ is intrinsically more unstable (lower activation energy), it will incorporate faster into the NW in a scenario where both gas precursors are in excess.

4. Tip-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy

Tip-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (TERS) was performed on Au-rich NWs that were previously dispersed on a Pt substrate. In particular, TERS mapping was performed on a NW lying parallel to the scan axis. The TERS signal is dominated by the three main Raman bands expected for a $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x$ alloy, i.e., Ge-Ge ($\sim 276 \text{ cm}^{-1}$), Si-Ge ($\sim 395 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) and Si-Si ($\sim 481 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) within a SiGe lattice as shown in Figure 4a, with an enhancement of the signal on top of the NW. This enhancement allows to spatially identify the NW through its chemical signature (Figure Suppl. 7). Averaging the Raman spectra within the depicted squares in the figure allows to compare the intrinsic TERS signal of the NW and the convoluted far-field (conventional) Raman signal (collected from the sample volume within the diffraction-limited hotspot). Two main features arise when the tip is located on top of the NW: i) an enhancement of the overall Raman signal and ii) the emerging of a doublet peak at ~ 508 and $\sim 520 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Both features are unique to the NWs. As discussed in the main text, it is argued that the appearance of the doublet peak, linked to strained Si states, matches well with the inclusion of Au into Si-rich clusters. This would explain the observed radial distributions of i) these strained Si states, ii) Au content and iii) density of clusters.

Figure Suppl. 7. TERS signal maps of the Raman spectra extracted from the scanned NW of shown Figure 4b for the three main emission bands of the $\text{Si}_{0.7}\text{Ge}_{0.3}$ alloy: a) Ge-Ge, b) SiGe and c) Si-Si. Scales are baselined to the maximum intensity of those peaks outside the NW in order to subtract the convoluted far-field (conventional) Raman signal to the actual intrinsic TERS signal.

5. Electrical characterization of nanowires:

5.1. Electrical measurements to non-tapered Au-free nanowires:

The analysis of the resistance-power (R-P) curves of Figure Suppl. 8a from the measured I-V curves (shown in the upper inset as a reference) shows a non-negligible bidirectional (or back-to-back) Schottky barrier for temperatures below 350 K. A degenerated semiconductor behavior is observed at higher temperatures, as expected from a heavily doped SiGe alloy. Yet, the barrier behaves as anticipated from the thermionic emission law, and fully vanishes for $P > 2 \mu\text{W}$ at all temperature ranges by the combined effects of the increasing external voltage (bias voltage)

applied and the rise in temperature produced by joule dissipated heat. In this way, for $P > 2 \mu\text{W}$, the slope in the R-P is totally attributed to the self-heating of the NW. Following the R_0 (R at $P = 0$) evolution as a function of temperature (T), a first reduction of R_0 as T increased from 300 K to 400 K due to the weakening of the Schottky barrier effective resistance (R_{SI}) is appreciated. Then, a linear increase of R_0 takes place when the temperature coefficient of resistance (α) starts to be the driving mechanism for the R_0 increase. Figure Suppl. 8b clearly shows how the evolution of R_0 as a function of temperature can be described as the sum of both aforementioned contributions:

$$R_0(T) = R_\alpha + R_{SI} = R_0^* (1 + \alpha\Delta T) + A \cdot T^2 \exp\left(q \frac{\Phi_{BE}}{k_B T}\right) \quad \text{S. Eq. 5}$$

Where, q is the elementary charge, k_B is the Boltzmann constant, Φ_{BE} is the Schottky barrier effective potential, R_0^* denotes the resistance at zero power at the reference temperature and ΔT is the temperature change with respect to that reference temperature. Therefore, the increase of R_0 at temperatures lower than 400 K can be attributed to an increase in the barrier effective resistance R_{SI} . Extrapolating the linear trend of $T > 400$ K the exponential decrease of R_{SI} could be extracted and fitted as function of T . With this approach, a barrier height of 0.36 eV was found.

Finally, it is worth mentioning the loss of linearity at higher temperatures ($T > 550$ K), only appreciable in the 550 K R-P curve of Figure Suppl. 8a. This loss of linearity is very likely related to an intrinsic semiconductor behavior, where above a certain temperature, the number of free carriers grow exponentially and eventually outnumber those of ionized impurities. In this way, both the Schottky and intrinsic regions represent temperature limits ($350 \text{ K} < T < 550 \text{ K}$) for the thermal evaluation of the NW using electrothermal methods (AC 3- ω in this case) as a linear behavior of R_{NW} with T is required.

Figure Suppl. 8. a) Current-voltage curves measured on the studied SiGe NW. b) Resistance-power curves at different temperatures. c) Variation of $R_0 = R(P=0)$ of each R-P curve as a function of temperature.

5.2. Electrical measurements to Au-rich nanowires:

In this section some additional data is provided concerning the assessment of electrical properties of NWs grown under high B₂H₆ conditions (>13 mPa) such as sample C₃. As it is stated in section 3.2, the presence of large contact barriers in the NW - very likely related to the presence of high amounts of Au within those NW - make their electrical measurement challenging. Figure Suppl. 9 shows an example of curves measured at 350 and 575 K. As it can be appreciated, the temperature increase is here incapable of overcoming the large barriers in the same way as sample C₁ (9.2 mPa) presented in Figure Suppl. 8.

Figure Suppl. 9. Example of current vs voltage (a) and equivalent power vs resistance (b) of a NW grown under high diborane conditions (19 mPa). The inset in (b) illustrates a SEM image of the suspended NW measured, showing a large tapering.

6. Thermal conductivity evaluation with 3- ω method:

The assessment of the thermal conductivity was performed using the AC 3- ω method, using the single suspended NW (see Figure 5) both as sample to study and as resistor as described by Lu et. Al. [3]. If a low frequency input is used, the heating/cooling transients can be considered in quasi-equilibrium since the temperature increase varies slowly enough that the thermal capacitance effects are negligible. Under this approximation, the thermal conductivity can be computed with the following expression:

$$\kappa = \frac{4 L R_0 i^3 (\partial R / \partial T)}{\pi^4 A V_{3\omega}} \quad \text{S. Eq. 6}$$

Where $\partial R / \partial T$ is the thermal coefficient of resistance, R is the NW thermal resistance at the temperature studied and L is the NW length and $V_{3\omega} / i^3$ can be found experimentally from the slope of a linear fit of the $V_{3\omega}$ versus applied current plot (Figure Suppl. 10). The validity of this assumption was checked for the frequency used (235 Hz) once κ was estimated and assuming a thermal capacity of the nanowire approximately equal to bulk [4–6]. S. Eq. 6 will be valid if the characteristic thermal time constant of the NW $\gamma = L^2 / \pi^2 \alpha$ is negligible compared to the period of the thermal oscillations ($2 \cdot \omega^{-1}$). In this case the thermal diffusivity $\alpha = \kappa / \rho C_p$ was assessed to be $4.3 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ and therefore the estimated thermal time constant was 5.9 μs , significantly smaller than the applied thermal oscillations (677 μs).

Figure Suppl. 10. Third harmonic signal of the measured NW as a function of i^3 at 400 K.

The 3rd harmonic signal was acquired using a SR630 Lock-in amplifier. However, since the experimental set-up consisted in a balance resistor in series with the studied NW fed by the same lock-in voltage output source (see Figure Suppl. 11), some corrections need to be made in the recorded signal. This is due to the fact that in this configuration the complete 3- ω component is in the current instead of the voltage. Therefore, reading the voltage drop across the NW just partially accounts for a fraction of the whole 3- ω signal. According to Xing et. Al. [7], this correction can simply be made using a voltage divider relationship:

$$V_{3\omega} = V_3 \frac{R_B + R_{NW}}{R_B} \quad \text{S. Eq. 7}$$

Where V_3 is the lock-in 3rd harmonic acquired signal at the NW terminals and R_B and R_{NW} are the balance and NW electrical resistances respectively.

Figure Suppl. 11. Electrical set-up for 3- ω measurements. The NW is allocated in series with a balance resistor and the excitation is applied using the Lock-in output voltage generator.

7. Seebeck measurements:

As described also in the experimental section, the Seebeck coefficient evaluation was carried by direct measurements on the voltage difference at the material ends obtained when a controlled thermal difference ΔT is set in this same direction:

$$S = \frac{dV}{dT} = \frac{\Delta V_{oc}}{\Delta T} \quad S. Eq. 8$$

In order to create the controlled ΔT at the NWs ends, an ad-hoc microfabricated devices including suspended platforms was used. The fabrication of the microdevices was carried done at IMB-CNM clean room facilities, (Barcelona, Spain) through a series of photolithography, metal evaporation and etching processes detailed – together with device architecture and operating principles – in [8,9]. NWs grown in micro-trenches between the suspended platform and the bulk could be driven to a controlled temperature by the use of a built-in tungsten micro-heater on the platform as Figure Suppl. 12 illustrates.

Figure Suppl. 12. Schematic showing the characterization device. Red arrows indicate the heat flow path, dissipated from the suspended platform built-in heater towards the bulk silicon, acting as the cold heat sink.

Since the aforementioned heaters offer a linear resistance to temperature relationship, they could also be calibrated and used to measure the platform temperature (T_{HT}) while heating. On the other hand, the bulk side is capable to efficiently dissipate the heat and therefore it is thermalized to the substrate temperature. Nevertheless, its temperature (T_B) was also controlled by the use of a second resistor over the bulk surface. Therefore, the controlled thermal gradient can be defined as $\Delta T = T_{HT} - T_B$. Simultaneously, the open circuit voltage response V_{oc} was measured.

In practice, several measurements of V_{oc} and ΔT were made at each bulk temperature, and a linear fit was used in order to improve the accuracy of the measurement, being the slope of the fitting the measured Seebeck coefficient as it can be seen in Figure Suppl. 13 where the raw V_{oc} vs ΔT values are shown.

Figure Suppl. 13. Open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) measured at increasing temperature differences ΔT and bulk temperatures. The slope for each line fit corresponds to the measured Seebeck coefficient.

8. Phonon modelling:

This section describes the lattice thermal conductivity (κ) model illustrated in Figure 6c. The estimation of κ was carried out using the Boltzmann transport equation with the relaxation-time approximation as proposed by Wang et al. [10]:

$$\kappa = \frac{k_B^4 T^3}{2 \pi^2 v_s \hbar^3} \int_0^{\hbar\omega_c/k_B\theta_D} \frac{\tau(T, y) y^4}{e^y (e^y - 1)^2} dy \quad S. Eq. 9$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, \hbar is the reduced Planck constant, $y \equiv \hbar\omega/k_B T$, v_s is the velocity of sound, θ_D is the Debye temperature and, and ω_c is the cut-off frequency. By integrating the whole frequency spectrum, S. Eq. 9 allows to estimate the lattice thermal conductivity. The phonon scattering terms $\tau(T, y)$ are added following the Matthiessen rule:

$$\frac{1}{\tau} = \sum \frac{1}{\tau_i(T, y)} = \tau_U^{-1} + \tau_N^{-1} + \tau_A^{-1} + \tau_B^{-1} + \tau_\eta^{-1} \quad S. Eq. 10$$

with τ_U the Umklapp scattering, τ_N the boron impurity scattering, τ_A the alloy phonon scattering, τ_B the boundary scattering, and τ_η the phonon-surface bond order imperfection scattering rate.

Table Suppl. 3 summarizes the referenced list of expressions used to calculate each one of the described scattering mechanisms. Note that the SVR estimation requires the parametrization of the x-y coordinates of the NW profile as described in Suppl. Section 1. Complementary, Table Suppl. 4 summarizes the referenced list of parameters employed in the model.

Table Suppl. 3. Summary the referenced expressions used to compute the different scattering mechanisms considered in the thermal conductivity model.

Scattering mechanism	Expression	Reference
Umklapp	$\tau_U^{-1} = \frac{(1-x)}{\tau_U^{Si}} + \frac{x}{\tau_U^{Ge}}$ $\frac{1}{\tau_U^i} = B_i \cdot \omega^2 \cdot T \cdot e^{-\frac{C_i}{T}}$	[10]
Impurity	$\tau_N^{-1} = N \cdot A_n \cdot \omega^4$	[11]
Alloy	$\tau_A^{-1} = x \cdot (1-x) \cdot A_{SiGe} \cdot \omega^4$	[10]
Boundary	$\tau_B^{-1} = \frac{v_B}{\phi_{NW}} \cdot (1-p)$ $v_B = \frac{1}{\left(\frac{1-x}{(v_B^{Si})^2} + \frac{x}{(v_B^{Ge})^2} \right)^{1/2}}$	[12]
Surface/roughness	$\tau_\eta^{-1} = A_\eta \cdot \omega^4 \cdot SVR$ $SVR = \int_0^L \frac{8 \int_0^L \sqrt{[\partial x(t)/\partial t]^2 + [\partial y(t)/\partial t]^2} dt}{L \pi \phi(t)}$	[13]

Table Suppl. 4. Summary the referenced parameters used in the thermal conductivity model.

Parameter	Symbol	Value	Reference
Umklapp scattering coefficients (Si)	B_{Si}	$1.51 \cdot 10^{19}$ s/K	[11]
	C_{Si}	139.8 K	[11]
Umklapp scattering coefficients (Ge)	B_{Ge}	$2.91 \cdot 10^{19}$ s/K	[10]
	C_{Si}	69.34 K	[10]
Speed of sound (Si)	v_B^{Si}	6400 m/s	[11]
Speed of sound (Ge)	v_B^{Ge}	3900 m/s	[10]
Cutoff frequency	ω_C	43.8 THz	[11]
Alloy scattering coefficient	A_{SiGe}	$3.01 \cdot 10^{-41}$ s ³	[10]
Impurity scattering coefficient	A_N	$8.62 \cdot 10^{-64}$ s ³	[11]
Roughness scattering coefficient	A_η	$1.86 \cdot 10^{-51}$ s ³	[13]

For the studied NW, a doping level of $5 \cdot 10^{18}$ cm⁻³ was assumed, along with a germanium concentration of $x=0.35$, a core NW diameter of 87 nm, and a surface to volume ratio $SVR = 0.15$ nm⁻¹ (equivalent to 3.3 times que equivalent of a perfect cylinder with the aforementioned core diameter).

9. Estimation of uncertainty:

The main sources of error in the calculation of the thermal conductivity arises from the determination of the dR/dT ($\sim 5.8\%$), the $V_{3\omega}/i^3$ ($\sim 2.1\%$) and the NW diameter ϕ_{NW} ($\sim 5.2\%$) (from the SEM images). In the case of the electrical conductivity estimation, the error arises from the fitting of the R-P curves at $P=0$ (R_0) ($\sim 0.9\%$) and, again, the NW diameter ϕ_{NW} . Finally, the error in the Seebeck coefficient arises from the estimation of the true ΔT , since the error direct measurement of the V_{OC} can be neglected. The error in the ΔT arises from the calibration of the temperature coefficient of resistance TCR ($\sim 3\%$) of both suspended microheater and bulk microresistor, and for each case, the resistance measurement itself ($< 0.5\%$). The power output of the harvesting devices simply depends on the estimation of the device resistance and the V_{OC} , which both have marginal error ($< 0.5\%$). In all the tree cases, - and for all the derived properties, such as the zT - the error was propagated assuming that all sources were independent, as:

$$o(a) = \sqrt{\sum o(i)^2} \quad S. Eq. 11$$

Where $o(i)$ denotes the relative error of each source of a .

References:

- [1] J. Gilfrich, Handbook of X-Ray Spectrometry: Methods and Techniques Edited by: Rene E. Van Grieken and Andrzej A. Markowicz Published by Marcel Dekker, Inc., New York, 1993; xiv + 704 pp., \$195, ISBN 0-8247-8483-9, 1994. <https://doi.org/10.1002/xrs.1300230110>.
- [2] K.K. Lew, L. Pan, E.C. Dickey, J.M. Redwing, Effect of growth conditions on the composition and structure of Si_{1-x}Ge_x nanowires grown by vapor-liquid-solid growth, J Mater Res. 21 (2006) 2876–2881. <https://doi.org/10.1557/jmr.2006.0349>.
- [3] L. Lu, W. Yi, D.L. Zhang, 3ω method for specific heat and thermal conductivity measurements, Review of Scientific Instruments. 72 (2001) 2996–3003. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.1378340>.
- [4] C. Marchbanks, Z. Wu, Reduction of heat capacity and phonon group velocity in silicon nanowires, Journal of Applied Physics. 117 (2015) 21–24. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4913453>.
- [5] Y. Zhang, J.X. Cao, Y. Xiao, X.H. Yan, Phonon spectrum and specific heat of silicon nanowires, Journal of Applied Physics. 102 (2007). <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.2811862>.
- [6] Y.F. Zhu, J.S. Lian, Q. Jiang, Modeling of the Melting Point, Debye Temperature, Thermal Expansion Coefficient, and the Specific Heat of Nanostructured Materials, The Journal of Physical Chemistry C. 113 (2009) 16896–16900. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp902097f>.
- [7] C. Xing, C. Jensen, T. Munro, B. White, H. Ban, M. Chirtoc, Thermal property characterization of fine fibers by the 3ω technique, Appl Therm Eng. 71 (2014) 589–595. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.applthermaleng.2014.06.022>.
- [8] I. Donmez Noyan, M. Dolcet, M. Salleras, A. Stranz, C. Calaza, G. Gadea, M. Pacios Pujadó, Á. Morata, A. Tarancón, L. Fonseca, M. Pacios, A. Morata, A. Tarancon, L. Fonseca, All-silicon thermoelectric micro/nanogenerator including a heat exchanger for harvesting applications, J Power Sources. 413 (2019) 125–133. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2018.12.029>.
- [9] L. Fonseca, J.-D. Santos, A. Roncaglia, D. Narducci, C. Calaza, M. Salleras, I. Donmez, A. Tarancon, A. Morata, G. Gadea, L. Belsito, L. Zulian, Smart integration of silicon nanowire arrays in all-silicon thermoelectric micro-nanogenerators, Semicond Sci Technol. 31 (2016) 084001. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0268-1242/31/8/084001>.
- [10] Z. Wang, N. Mingo, Diameter dependence of SiGe nanowire thermal conductivity, Appl Phys Lett. 97 (2010) 101903. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3486171>.
- [11] Y. Ohishi, J. Xie, Y. Miyazaki, Y. Aikebaier, H. Muta, K. Kurosaki, S. Yamanaka, N. Uchida, T. Tada, Thermoelectric properties of heavily boron- and phosphorus-doped silicon, Jpn J Appl Phys. 54 (2015) 071301. <https://doi.org/10.7567/JJAP.54.071301>.

- [12] H. Lee, D. Vashaee, D.Z. Wang, M.S. Dresselhaus, Z.F. Ren, G. Chen, Effects of nanoscale porosity on thermoelectric properties of SiGe, *J Appl Phys.* 107 (2010) 094308. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.3388076>.
- [13] H.-Y. Yang, Y.-L. Chen, W.-X. Zhou, G.-F. Xie, N. Xu, Ultra-low thermal conductivity of roughened silicon nanowires: Role of phonon-surface bond order imperfection scattering, *Chinese Physics B.* (2020) 0–14. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1674-1056/ab99af>.